

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSES OF
REPRESENTATIVE REGIONS**

(BASELINE STUDY)

**THE CASE OF CENTRAL WEST ZONE AND NORTH ZONE OF
SENEGAL**

Final Report

**(Appendix E of CIRAWA_D2.2_Socio-Econ. and Env.
Analysis_V.6.0_2024_06_29)**

**West African Centre for Water, Irrigation and Sustainable Agriculture,
University for Development Studies
(WACWISA-UDS)
Tamale, Ghana
(Contact: saaditt@uds.edu.gh)**

June 2024

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	V
LIST OF FIGURES	VIII
ABBREVIATIONS	IX
CHAPTER 1.....	1
BACKGROUND, OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY	1
1.1 The CIRAWA Project	1
1.2 Study Area	2
1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)	3
1.4 Methodology (Summary).....	3
CHAPTER 2.....	4
SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLDS	4
2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members	4
2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses.....	8
2.3 Farm Sizes and Types	9
2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes	9
2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming	11
2.3.3 Land preparation methods	11
2.3.4 Numbers of farm plots and their locations	12
2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming	13
2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots	13
2.4.2 Use of inorganic fertilizers	15
2.4.3 Use of organic fertilizers	16
CHAPTER 3.....	17
FARMING SYSTEMS BY ZONES	17
3.1 Crop-Based Systems.....	17
3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures	17
3.1.2 Planting materials and sources	20
3.1.3 Soil amendment practices	22
3.1.4 Crop production constraints	23
3.2 Livestock-Based Systems	24
3.2.1 Animal ownership and management.....	24
3.2.2 Animal breeds, sources, and characteristics.....	28
3.2.3 Livestock constraints	33
3.3 Irrigation Farming Systems.....	40

3.3.1 Irrigation types, crops cultivated, and soil amendments.	40
3.3.2 Percieved success of irrigation types and irrigation constraints	42
Chapter 4	44
OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS	44
4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources	44
4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale	44
4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources	46
4.4 Expenditure by Households	49
CHAPTER 5.....	51
HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY	51
5.1 Household Food Security.....	51
5.2 Household Dietary Diversity.....	52
5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day - HHH.....	52
5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHH	54
CHAPTER 6.....	56
HOUSEHOLD RESOURCES AND USE	56
6.1 General Changes in Land Use Over Time	56
6.1.1 Overall changes over 10 to 50 years	56
6.1.2 Perceptions of land use changes by HHHs and WiHHs over the past 10 years	57
6.1.3 Comparison of land use changes/transitions in the past 5, 10, 30 and 50 years in the zones as perceived by HHHs and WiHHs.....	60
6.2 Yields Change Over Time.....	63
CHAPTER 7.....	66
AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES	66
7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices	66
7.2 Factors Influencing Use of Agroecological Practices	69
7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes.....	72
7.3.1 Types of agro-wastes and their uses	72
7.3.2 Quantities of agro waste generated by households	76
CHAPTER 8.....	77
CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES	77
8.1 Evidence of Climate Change.....	77
8.2 Climate Change Adaptation Measures.....	78
8.3 Anti-environmental practices	80
CHAPTER 9.....	81

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS	81
9.1 Summary	81
9.2 Recommendations	83
REFERENCES	84
APPENDICES	85

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs, and household interviews conducted.....	3
Table 2.1: Men and women headed households in CWZ and NZ	4
Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in CWZ and NZ.....	5
Table 2.3: Average ages of HHHs and spouses	5
Table 2.5: Length of time HHHs (men) have been in the Zones	6
Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs and spouses	6
Table 2.7: Average household size distributions	7
Table 2.10: Major and Minor Occupations of Respondents – Central West Zone	9
Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations – North Zone.....	9
Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in acres) HHH	10
Table 2.13: Methods of land acquisition for farming	11
Table 2.15: Numbers of farm plots, locations, and walking time to farms (HHH and WiHHs) ...	13
Table 2.17: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots (North Zone)	14
Table 2.18: Inorganic fertilizer utilization	15
Table 2.19: Farmers' perceived crops response to inorganic fertilizers	15
Table 2.21: Organic fertilizer utilization.....	16
Table 3.1: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in households- HHH in Central West Zone	17
Table 3.2: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in households- HHH in North Zone	18
Table 3.3: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – Central West Zone	19
Table 3.4: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – North Zone	19
Table 3.5: Types and Sources of planting materials- Central West Zone- HHHs	20
Table 3.6: Types and Sources of planting materials- NorthZone – HHHs	20
Table 3.7: Types and Sources of planting materials- Central West Zone- WiHHs	21
Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- North Zone - WiHHs	21
Table 3.9: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH	22
Table 3.10: Soil amendment practices in households- WiHH.....	22
Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Central West Zone for the years 2022 and 2023.....	25
Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Central West Zone for the years 2022 and 2023.....	26
Table 3.13: Men livestock ownership and sales in the North Zone for the years 2022 and 2023 .	27

Table 3.14: Women livestock ownership and sales in the NorthZone for the years 2022 and 2023	27
Tables 3.15: Livestock breeds reared by men in Central West Zone and North Zone	29
Tables 3.16: Livestock breeds reared by women in Central West Zone and North Zone	29
Table 3.17 Men and Women main source of animal breeds in Central West Zone	30
Table 3.18 Main source of animal breeds in the NorthZone	31
Table 3.19: Special characteristics of animal breeds in Central West Zone	32
Table 3.20: Special characteristics of animal breeds in NorthZone.....	33
Table 3.21: Types of irrigation undertaken.....	40
Table 3.22: Crops grown under irrigation.....	41
Table 3.23 Types of Soil Amendments Used.	41
Table 3.24: Perceived level of success of different irrigation types	42
Table 3.25: Irrigation constraints	43
Table 4.3: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold according men and women in the Zones	46
Table 4.5: Household expenditure on various items by men (HHH) and women (WiHH) in 12 months (2022/2023).....	49
Table 5.1: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022.....	51
Table 5.2: Household head Dietary Diversity (HDDS)	53
Table 5.3: Women in household dietary diversity (WiHDDS).....	54
Table 6.1: HHHs’ perceptions of general changes in land use overtime (past 10 to 50 years)	56
Table 6.2: WiHHs’ perceptions of general changes in land use overtime (past 10 to 50 years) ...	57
Table 6.3: General changes in land use according to HHHs in CWZ over the past 10 years.....	58
Table 6.4: General changes in land use by HHHs in NZ over the past 10 years	58
Item	58
NorthZone	58
Table 6.5: Changes in land use as perceived by WiHHs in CWZ over the past 10 years	59
Item	59
Central West Zone	59
Table 6.6: Changes in land use as perceived by WiHHs in NZover the past 10 years	59
Table 6.7: Land use changes/transition over time in Central West Zone and NorthZone as perceived by HHHs.....	61
Table 6.7: Land use changes/transition over time in Central West Zone and NorthZone as perceived by HHHs.....	62
Table 7.1: HHHs awareness and use agroecological technologies in Central West Zone.....	66
Table 7.2: WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central West Zone	67
Table 7.3: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in NorthZone	68
Table 7.4 WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in NorthZone	69

Tables 7.5: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men and women in Central West Zone	70
Tables 7.6: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men and women in North Zone	71
Table 7.7: Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Central West Zone	73
Table 7.8 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Central West Zone.....	73
Table 7.9 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in NorthZone	75
Table 7.10 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Senegal River Valley Zone	75
Table 7.11 Quantities of agro waste generated per acre per season.....	76
Appendix 1:.....	85
The Method of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies (WSRF)	85
Appendix 3:.....	87
The Method of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies (WSRF)	87
Relative importance of non-farm sources of income in the past one year - HHHs	87
Relative importance of non-farm sources of income in the past one year - WiHHs	88
Household expenditure in 12 months (at time of survey) – HHH	89
(Weighted scores of ranked frequencies method).....	89

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1: Average household size distribution	7
Figure 2.2: Distribution of household (HH), individual men and individual women farm sizes.....	10
Figure 3.1 Relative importance of crop production constraints according to HHHs in CWZ and NZ	23
Figure 3.2 Relative importance of crop production constraints according to WiHHs zones.....	24
Figure 3.4 WiHHs cattle production constraints by zone	35
Figure 3.5 Goat production constraints by zone (Household head).....	36
Figure 3.7 Sheep production constraints by zone(household head).....	37
Figure 3.8 Sheep production constraints by zone(women).....	38
Figure 3.9 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by zone.....	39
Figure 3.10 Fowl (chicken) production constraints by zone(women)	39
Figure 4.1: Non-farm sources of income in the past one year - HHHs.....	48
Figure 4.2: Non-farm sources of income in the past one year - WiHHs.....	48
Figure 4.2: HHHs expenditure in 12 months (2022) – (weighted averages of main expenditure items).....	50
Figure 6.1: Reasons for increase in yields over time by in NZ zone by HHHs (No information was obtained from CWZ).....	63
Figure 6.2: Reasons given by WiHHS for increase in yields over time in CWZ	64
Figure 6.3 Reasons given by HHHs for decrease in yields over time in CWZ.....	64
Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields in CWZ and NZ	65

ABBREVIATIONS

AU	African Union
CWZ	Central West Zone
EU	European Union
FGDs	Focus Group Discussions
GD	Green Deal (of the EU)
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HHH(s)	Household Head(s)
KIIs	Key Informant Interviews
NZ	North Zone
UN	United Nations
WiHH(s)	Women In Household(s)
WP	Work Package

CHAPTER 1

BACKGROUND, OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

1.1 The CIRAWA Project

CIRAWA – Agroecological Strategies for Resilient Farming in West Africa, is an EU-funded project, which aims to “unlock the potential of the agro-ecology in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling the climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices”. CIRAWA is working on innovative agroecological approaches using, among others, the following strategies:

- 1) valorisation of agro-wastes and bio-based fertiliser production;
- 2) production of high-quality seeds;
- 3) saline soil reclamation through phytoremediation; and
- 4) soil fertility, water, and crop management practices.

These strategies are being deployed in 4 countries in West Africa; Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal, and The Gambia.

The CIRAWA Project (and three similar ones in North, East, and Central Africa) arose out of the EU-AU collaborative efforts in agriculture and the focus of the EU to facilitate a green transition according to its Green Deal (GD) objectives, which basically define the EU’s climate strategy to reach net zero emissions by 2050. It is also in line with the EU-Africa biodiversity strategy which seeks to create a circular economy.

Even though the original proposal indicated that certain specific activities would be undertaken in the different countries, it has been pointed out and agreed that almost all the proposed intervention activities are required in all the countries. Thus, the following activities are expected to be undertaken in the various countries in consultation with farmers with regard to their needs and requirements.

- 1) Characterisation of local soils: fertility studies
- 2) Characterisation of locally available manures and crop-residues, protocol definition and implementation and production of innovative vermi-compost and bio-based fertilisers
- 3) Characterisation of locally available crop-residues and production of materials for household energy production.
- 4) Soil conservation practices
- 5) Saline soil reclamation strategies through an integrated approach based on salt-tolerant species (phytoremediation)
- 6) Crop management decision support system: irrigation, and fertilisation modules.
- 7) High-quality seeds production and multiplication, with consideration given to characterization and improvements of seeds of indigenous crops.
- 8) Water collection techniques: cloud/fog harvesting.

- 9) Strategies to increase access of farmers to markets.
- 10) Awareness creation campaigns to promote agro-ecological farming systems.
- 11) Farming system cross-border best-practices integration platform
- 12) Promoting participatory and inclusive governance especially, for women and youth.

In Senegal, the Central West Zone (CWZ) and the North Zone (NZ) including the river Delta and part of the Senegal river Valley) were chosen for the implementation of the CIRAWA project. These two zones have significant contrasting characteristics.

1.2 Study Area

The Republic of Senegal is in West Africa occupying a total area of 197,000 sq km² with a population of about 17 million people and an overall density of 92 persons per km². Agriculture is the primary source of livelihood for many Senegalese employing about 60% of the workforce and accounting for about 15% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Agriculture is predominantly smallholder, traditional, and rainfed.

Climate and Vegetation

Senegal's climate is characterized by a dry season which lasts from November to May and a rainy season which starts in June and ends in October. Average temperatures are high in the interior parts of the country at about 28⁰C and lower at the coast at about 24⁰C (Amy et al., 2021). The climate of the NZ (Part of the Senegal River Valley and Delta) is dry and rainfall is often lower, ranging from 200 mm to 600 mm annually between May and September. From the middle river valley to the delta, the Senegal river forms the basis for all agricultural activities. The CWZ also has a Sahelian climate. Average temperatures typically range from 25⁰C to 30⁰C

Land Use and Soil

In the CWZ and NZ, agriculture is the predominant land use. Clays or sandy loams make up most of the alluvial soil in the NZ (Senegal river valley and delta), The NZ is known to be vital in water supply, agriculture, fishing, and other economic activities in the area due to the presence of the river. Agriculture, animal husbandry, and fishing are predominant in this region. According to Ndiaye et al. (2020) topography, geology, climate, and hydrography of the CWZ of Senegal contribute to distinct soil types with varying capacities for agriculture. There are four varieties of soil: sandy, clay, clay-sandy, and salty soils. These types differ in texture, structure, and organic matter concentration (Ndiaye et al., 2020). These zones are also susceptible to a variety of natural disasters, including droughts, floods, and the mineralization of the soil brought on by the application of chemical and mineral fertilizers. The zones are noted for agricultural irrigation

1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)

The overall objective of WP2 is for qualitative and quantitative assessment of farmers' and communities' needs and requirements, and their resource availability and use as well as identification of the available agro-ecological practices taking place in the different locations and how they are adapted to local needs and contexts. It also provides baseline information on social, economic, and environmental indicators against which project progress and effectiveness during implementation can be monitored and evaluated.

1.4 Methodology (Summary)

Qualitative and quantitative research designs were used in the information and data collection from the two zones. Focus group discussions (FGDs) and key informant interviews (KIIs) were used to collect most of the qualitative information while in-depth household interviews were used to collect most of the quantitative information. Data collection protocols were designed and used to solicit information from farmers and other stakeholders on farmers' requirements and needs as part of the socio-economic and environmental baseline survey. It involved the use of enumerators and supervisors who were conversant with the different environments and the languages spoken by the people. They, however, had to be trained in the data collection process so that they could interact effectively to tease out the important requirements and needs of farmers and community members. WACWISA-UDS teams together with personnel of the CIRAWA Partner in Senegal, ISRA, trained the supervisors and enumerators and took part in some of the field activities. The numbers of communities and households sampled from the two zones are highlighted in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs, and household interviews conducted.

Zone	Number of Focus Group Discussions (Adults)	Number of Focus Group Discussions (Youth)	Number of Key Informant Interviews	Household interviews	
				Men	Women
Central West Zone	10	5	10	15	15
North Zone	10	10	20	35	35
Total	20	15	30	50	50

Source: Field Survey, May/June 2023

CHAPTER 2

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLDS

2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members

Table 2.1 presents information from both men (HHHs) and women (WiHHs) with regard to household heads. Information from the men suggests that there are no women headed households in the Central West Zone (CWZ) and very few in the NZ (Senegal River Valley and delta). This is usually the case in most African societies where even when women are de facto heads of households, they prefer to leave that title to a male adult in the household. The information obtained from the women (WiHHs questionnaire) however contradicts the information given by the men (HHHs) as shown in the table (Table 2.1). It seems there was a misunderstanding of the question that was asked with regard to household heads. Both the men and women are claiming to be household heads.

Table 2.1: Men and women headed households in CWZ and NZ

Zone	HHH				WiHH			
	Men headed households		Women headed households		Men headed households		Women headed households	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central West Zone	15	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	15	100.0
North Zone	34	97.1	1	2.9	2	5.7	33	94.3

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.2 shows that male farmers (HHHs) in the CWZ and the NZ are 100% and 94.0% indigenes respectively. Only 5.7% of the HHHs in the NZ are non-indigenes. If a large majority of farmers are indigenes it means they are very conversant with customs and traditions of the areas with regards to land tenure and other local regulations. In the case of the women (WiHHs), 61.8% and 91.4% respectively are indigenes in the CWZ and the NZ. As many as 38.2% of the women in the CWZ are non-indigenes. That might have been as a result of marriage to indigenes in the CWZ.

Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in CWZ and NZ

Zone	HHH				WiHH*			
	Indigenes		Non-indigenes		Indigenes		Non-Indigenes	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central West Zone	15	100.0	0	0.0	21	61.8	13	38.2
North Zone	33	94.3	2	5.7	32	91.4	3	8.6

*The WiHHs are more than the sample sizes of 15 and 33 households respectively for the CWZ and the NZ . The likelihood is that the women respondents considered all the women in their households. Their husbands can have more than one wife each.

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.3: Average ages of HHHs and spouses

Zone	Ages (years) of HHHs (Men)				Ages (years) of their spouses (women)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central West Zone	57.3	13.49	72	36	37.0	5.66	41	33
North Zone	58.5	11.56	87	31	42.8	10.37	52	28
Total	57.9	12.53	87	31	39.9	8.02	52	28

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

The average age of household heads in the CWZ is 57.3, while in the NZ it is 58.5, with both zones showing low standard deviations. For women household heads, the average age is 37 in the CWZ and 42.8 in the NZ. These figures suggest a youthful demographic among women, indicating that more young women are engaged in farming compared to men in both zones.

Table 2.4: Crop farming experiences of HHHs

Zone	Crop farming experience (HHHs)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central West Zone	38.5	10.64	60	25
North Zone	31.5	12.00	58	5
Total	35.0	11.32	60	5

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

All the men farmers (100%) in the CWZ and 97.1% in the NZ have been in their present locations for over 20 years (Table 2.5). They are all, therefore, very conversant with the land tenure, the farming practices, and local dos and don'ts.

The educational status of HHHs (men) is given in Table 2.6. Only 11.8% and 12.9% of them in the CWZ and NZ respectively have not had any form of formal education (Table 2.6). That means most of the farmers in the Zones in Senegal have had some form of formal education. Most of them have had primary, junior, secondary, and non-formal education (Table 2.6). It is worth noting that 2 out of 17 men farmers (11.8%) and 3 out of 31 (9.9%) men farmers in the

CWZ and NZ respectively have had tertiary education. The information given to the spouses is ignored due to the very low responses to the question. Information on the women's educational status was provided for only 2 and 3 spouses in CWZ and NZ s respectively. It may be necessary to find out more about the status of the education level of the women farmers in the zones.

Table 2.5: Length of time HHHs (men) have been in the Zones

	< 5 years		5 – 10 years		11 – 20 years		> 20 years	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central West Zone	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	15	100.0
North Zone	0	0.0	1	0.0	0	0.0	34	97.1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs and spouses

Level of Education	Central West Zone				North Zone			
	HHHs		Spouses		HHHs		Spouses	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Primary	5	29.4	1	50.0	14	45.2	2	66.7
JHS/MSLC	4	23.5	0	0.0	1	3.2	0	0.0
SHS/Technical/O&A-Levels	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	6.5	0	0.0
Tertiary	2	11.8	1	50.0	3	9.9	0	0.0
Non-formal (completed)	4	23.5	0	0.0	7	22.6	1	33.3
Non-formal (Not completed)	0	0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
None	2	11.8	0	0.0	4	12.9	0	0.0
Total	17	100	2	100.0	31	100.0	3	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Household (HH) size distributions in the zones are presented in Table 2.7 and Figure 2.1. The average household size in the CWZ is very high, 18.7, with a standard deviation of 5.56, and that in the NZ is 13.4, with a standard deviation of 2.17. The household sizes in the two zones of Senegal are generally high. The maximum figures for the various categories of household members in the CWZ are unbelievable, between 20 and 22 (Table 2.7). One hopes that there was not a misunderstanding of the information required. The maximum figures given for the NZ (between 7 and 12) are much more realistic.

Table 2.7: Average household size distributions

Zone		Male adults	Female adults	Male children	Female children	Total HH size
Central West Zone	Average	4.9	5.0	4.6	4.2	18.7
	Std. Dev.	7.06	7.28	4.88	5.06	5.56
	Max.	22	21	20	20	-
	Min.	1	1	1	1	-
NorthZone	Average	3.4	3.7	3.3	3.0	13.4
	Std. Dev.	2.02	2.24	2.64	1.75	2.17
	Max.	7	9	12	7	-
	Min.	1	1	0	0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023.

Figure 2.1: Average household size distribution

It is expected that the different categories of household members in the zones will contribute to farming and other household activities in different ways and in different proportions. As given in Table 2.8, most of the farming activities, such as land preparation, planting, weeding, harvesting and livestock care in the CWZ are carried out by male adults and male children. Female adults undertake household chores, and water and firewood provision while the female children assist in carrying water and firewood. The situation in the NZ is however different. Though considerable farming activities are undertaken by male adults, female adults also take part in planting, weeding, harvesting and care of livestock (Table 2.9). It is however surprising that male adults are the ones undertaking household chores in the NZ. Male children in the NZ contribute significantly to all the farming activities and the female children are involved in harvesting, livestock care as well as water provision for household use (Table 2.9).

Table 2.8 HH members contributions to farming and other activities (Central West Zone)

Farming and other activities of HH members	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	8	38.1	0	0.0	13	61.9	0	0.0	21
Planting	8	36.4	1	4.5	13	59.1	0	0.0	22
Weeding	8	40.0	0	0.0	12	60.0	0	0.0	20
Harvesting	8	30.8	3	11.5	13	50.0	2	7.7	26
Feeding animals	7	31.8	1	4.5	13	59.1	1	4.5	22
Shepherding livestock	5	62.5	0	0.0	3	37.5	0	0.0	8
Errands	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	2
HH Chores	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	1
Carrying water	1	7.7	4	30.8	0	0.0	8	61.5	13
Carrying firewood	1	6.3	5	31.3	0	0.0	10	62.5	16

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.9 HH members contributions to farming and other activities (North Zone)

Farming and other activities of HH members	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	29	74.4	1	2.6	9	23.1	0	0.0	39
Planting	28	56.0	7	14.0	14	28	1	2.0	50
Weeding	29	59.2	6	12.2	14	28.6	0	0.0	49
Harvesting	30	38.5	24	30.8	16	20.5	8	10.3	78
Feeding animals	17	44.7	9	23.7	10	26.3	2	5.3	38
Shepherding livestock	14	50.0	4	14.3	10	26.3	2	5.3	38
Errands	14	50.0	4	14.3	10	35.7	0	0.0	28
HH Chores	10	83.3	2	16.7	0	0.0	0	0.0	12
Carrying water	1	20.0	1	20.0	2	40.0	1	20.0	5
Financial contribution	1	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses

Tables 2.10 and 2.11 give the major and minor occupations of HHHs and their spouses in the CWZ and the NZ. Most of the respondents in the CWZ are salaried workers (52.9%). Only 17.6% of the respondents have farming as their major occupation even though 64.7% undertake arable crop farming as their minor occupation. It might have been better to target communities where farming is the predominant occupation. A considerable number (17.6%) also undertake livestock farming as their minor occupation. In the case of the NZ, a large majority of the men

respondents (96.7%) are arable crop farmers. They are also involved in several tasks as their minor occupations; the most prominent being livestock farming, as given in Table 2.11. The poor responses for the spouses (women) make it untenable to use the information to draw any inferences. The responses are for 2 and 4 women in CWZ and NZ respectively (Tables 2.10 and 2.11).

Table 2.10: Major and Minor Occupations of Respondents – Central West Zone

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses (women)	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (% Freq.)		Freq (% Freq.)	
Arable crop farming	3 (17.6)	11 (64.7)	0	1(50)
Livestock farming	0	3 (17.6)	0	0
Salaried worker	9 (52.9)	0	1 (50)	0
Tradesman (Bricklayer, carpenter, tailor etc.)	3 (17.6)	2 (11.8)	1 (50)	0
Others	2 (11.8)	1 (5.9)	0	1 (50)
Total	15 (100)	17 (100)	2 (100)	2 (100)

Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations – North Zone

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (% Freq.)		Freq (% Freq.)	
Arable crop farming	29 (96.7)	1 (3.6)	3(75)	0
Livestock farming	0	17 (60.7)	0	1 (33.3)
Fishing	0	2 (7.1)	0	0
Produce marketing (Crop)	0	1 (3.6)	0	0
Petty trading/food vending	0	1 (3.6)	0	0
Salaried worker	0	1 (3.6)	0	0
Others	1 (3.3)	5 (17.9)	1 (25)	2 (66.7)
Total	30 (100.0)	28 (100.0)	4 (100.0))	3 (100.0)

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023.

2.3 Farm Sizes and Types

2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes

Table 2.10 and Figure 2.2 give the average farm sizes of “household (HH) farms”, “individual men farms” and “individual women farms”. The three components add up to give the “household farm holdings”. Household farms are those managed by the HHH. They are held in trust for all members of the HH. The table and figure show wide differences in farm sizes between the two zones. Farm sizes in the CWZ are almost three times the sizes in the NZ . Also,

while the farm sizes of individual men and individual women are about the same in the CWZ, individual men farm sizes are about six times individual women farm sizes in the NZ . The women farms are mainly irrigated vegetable farms and that partly explains the small sizes. The relatively small standard deviations indicate that farm size variations within the zones are low. The wide differences in farm sizes between men in CWZ and NZ as well as between men and women explain to a large degree the kinds of household labour contributions indicated in Tables 2.8 and 2.9.

Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in acres) HHH

		Household (HH) farms (A)	Individual men farms (B)	Individual women farms (C)	Household farm holding (A+B+C)
Central West Zone	Average area	7.5	4.0	4.0	15.5
	Std. Dev.	4.9	0.0	2.4	3.67
	Max	17.0	4.0	6.0	-
	Min	0	4.0	0.01	-
North Zone	Average area	2.8	2.3	0.4	5.5
	Std. Dev.	3.0	3.6	0.2	2.3
	Max	15.0	13.0	0.5	-
	Min	0.4	0.5	0.2	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023.

Figure 2.2: Distribution of household (HH), individual men and individual women farm sizes

2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming

Table 2.13 shows the methods of land acquisition of the different types of farmlands by men and women for their farm operations in the CWZ and NZ . All the HH farmlands are inherited and about 42.9% of the land for individual women farms is also inherited in the CWZ. Thus, in the CWZ, about 56.2% of farmlands are inherited. Other main methods of land acquisition in the zone, mainly by women, include “owned/purchased” 26.0%, and rented, 12.3%. In the case of theNZ , 65.8% of the land is inherited and 21.1% is state-owned. As in the CWZ, most of the inherited land is used for the HH farms (Table 2.13). State-owned lands are usually acquired for individual men and women farms as indicated in the table.

Table 2.13: Methods of land acquisition for farming

Zones	Method of land acquisition	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central West Zone	Inheritance	16	100.0	1	100.0	24	42.9	41	56.2
	Leased	-	-	-	-	1	1.8	1	1.4
	Rented	-	-	-	-	9	16.1	9	12.3
	Borrowed (Free)	-	-	-	-	3	5.4	3	4.1
	Owned/ purchased	-	-	-	-	19	33.9	19	26.0
	Total	16	100.0	1	100.0	56	100.0	73	100.0
North Zone	Inheritance	20	62.5	4	36.4	1	25.0	25	65.8
	Leased	-	-	1	9.1	-	-	1	2.6
	Rented	1	3.1	-	-	-	-	1	2.6
	Borrowed (Free)	1	3.1	-	-	-	-	1	2.6
	Owned/ purchased	-	-	1	9.1	1	25.0	2	5.3
	State -Owned	2	6.3	4	36.4	2	50.0	8	21.1
	Total	24	75.0	10	91.0	4	100.0	38	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.3.3 Land preparation methods

Land preparation for cultivation in the CWZ is mainly by “no till”, hoe, animal traction and to a much less extent tractor (Table 2.14). That is the situation in the household farm plots. There was almost no response with respect to the individual men and individual women plots. There was no indication of the use of weedicides for land preparation, unless “no till” implied the use of weedicides.

In the case of the NZ, tractor use is the most prominent in all types of farm plots, followed by animal (horse) traction and then use of hoe. The hoe is used mainly on household plots (Table 2.14). There is very little use of the “no till” method and no use of weedicides. It will be good to know why weedicides are not used in the two zones.

Table 2.14: Methods of land preparation

Zones	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central West Zone	Tractor	2	12.5	0	0.0	-	-	2	11.8
	Hoe	3	18.8	0	0.0	-	-	3	17.6
	Weedicides	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Animal Traction	3	18.8	1	100	-	-	4	23.5
	No till (at the beginning)	8	50.0	0	0.0	-	-	8	47.1
	Total	16	100.0	1	100	-	-	17	100
North Zone	Tractor	20	62.5	5	45.5	2	66.7	27	58.7
	Hoe	4	12.5	0	0	0	0	4	8.7
	Weedicides	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Animal Traction	7	21.9	5	45.5	1	33.3	13	28.3
	No till (at the beginning)	1	3.1	1	9.1	0	0	2	4.3
	Total	32	100.0	11	100.0	3	100.0	46	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.3.4 Numbers of farm plots and their locations

As given in Table 2.15 a household holding (all farm plots in the HH) in the CWZ has about 30 farm plots while that of the NZ is about 47 plots. Most of the farms are “bush farms” (76.7% in CWZ and 95.7% in NZ) as opposed to “compound farms” which are usually found around homesteads in some areas. There are negligible individual men plots (3.3%) in the CWZ and very few individual women plots (8.5%) in the NZ . It is to be noted that the number of plots does not necessarily reflect the total farm sizes since a farm plot is a distinctly contiguous area of land in which particular crop or crop mixtures are cultivated irrespective of the size.

Since most of the farms are “bush farms”, they are located some distance from homesteads. It takes an average of about 30 minutes to walk from the homes to the farms in CWZ and about 40 minutes to walk to the farms in NZ (Table 2.15).

Table 2.15: Numbers of farm plots¹, locations, and walking time to farms (HHH and WiHHs)

Zones	Farm Plot Category	Compound farm		Bush farm		Number of farm plots	Average time spent to travel from home to farms (the bush farms)	
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq		Mean distance (minutes)	Standard deviation
Central West Zone	HH farm plots	1	14.3	15	65.2	16	28.9	14.03
	Individual men farm plots	-	-	1	4.3	1	30.0	.
	Individual women farm plots	6	85.7	7	30.4	13	NA	-
	Total	7	100.0	23	100.0	30	28.9	13.59
NorthZone	HH farm plots	1	50.0	31	68.9	32	34.4	31.79
	Individual men farm plots	0	0.0	11	24.4	11	40.9	39.17
	Individual women farm plots	1	50.0	3	6.7	4	115.0	134.00
	Total	2	100.0	45	100.0	47	41.2	50.76

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming

2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots

Farmers' (HHHs and WiHHs) perceived levels of soil fertility of their household and individual farms are presented in Tables 2.16 and 2.17. On average, most (55.7%) of the farmers in the CWZ, indicated that their farms were fertile, but they still required some external inputs and manure. This is followed by 32.6% of farmers who indicated that their soils were poor and could not produce without manure and/or external inputs (Table 2.16). Only a few women farmers in CWZ perceive their individual farms to be very fertile.

In the case of the NZ,, the majority (57.8%) perceive their farms to be fertile but still require some external inputs and manure. That is followed by 24.4% of farmers who perceive their soils to be very fertile (Table 2.17). Only 2.2% of farmers in the NZ perceive their farms to be of poor fertility.

¹ A farm plot refers to a distinctly contiguous area of land in which particular crop or crop mixtures are cultivated irrespective of the size.

Table 2.16: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots (CWZ)

Perceived fertility of the soil of different plots	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	-	-	-	-	3	11.5	3	7.0
Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	14	87.5	0	0.0	10	38.5	24	55.7
Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	2	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	4.7
Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	0	0.0	1	100	13	50.0	14	32.6
Total	16	100	1	100	26	100	43	100

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 2.17: Perceptions of fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots (North Zone)

Perceived fertility of the soil of different plots	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	6	19.4	3	27.3	2	66.7	11	24.4
Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	20	64.5	5	45.5	1	33.3	26	57.8
Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	4	12.9	3	27.3	0	0.0	7	15.6
Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	1	3.2	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	2.2
Total	31	100	11	100	3	100	45	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.4.2 Use of inorganic fertilizers

Many farmers in both zones, especially in the NZ applied inorganic fertilizers to their crops in the 2022 cropping season. About 51.6% and 89.1% of them did so in the CWZ and NZ respectively (Table 2.18). Most of the fertilizers were used on the HH farms, followed by the individual men farms. The application on the individual women farms in both the CWZ and the NZ were much less: 31.2% and 4.1% respectively (Table 2.18). It is not surprising that fewer women applied fertilizer to their farm plots. The use of inorganic fertilizer depends on the type of crops grown on the farm plots. Typically, inorganic fertilizers are used for cereal crops, particularly maize. Women tend to cultivate more legumes than cereals. That partly explains the relatively low use of inorganic fertilizers by women farmers.

Table 2.18: Inorganic fertilizer utilization

Farm Plots	Central West Zone				NorthZone			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	10	62.5	6	37.5	31	96.9	1	3.1
Individual men farm plots	1	100.0	0	0.0	8	72.7	3	27.3
Individual women farm plots (from WiHH)	5	38.5	8	61.5	2	66.7	1	33.3
Total	16	51.6	15	48.4	41	89.1	5	10.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Most of the farmers (over 91.3% and 89.1% respectively) who apply inorganic fertilizers in both the CWZ and the NZ believe the fertilizers are effective (Table 2.19). Only 8.7% and 10.9% of the farmers in the CWZ and the NZ respectively indicated that there is a negative crop response to inorganic fertilizers (Table 2.19).

Table 2.19: Farmers' perceived crops response to inorganic fertilizers

Farm Plot Category	Central West Zone				North Zone			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	11	91.7%	1	8.3%	31	96.9	1	3.1
Individual men farm plots	1	100.0	0	0.0	8	72.7	3	27.3
Individual women farm plots (from WiHH)	9	90.0	1	10.0	2	66.7	1	33.3
Total	21	91.3	2	8.7	41	89.1	5	10.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Quantities of fertilizers applied per unit area are relatively low especially in the CWZ. Average quantities of fertilizers applied per acre on HH farm plots in NZ are more than twice that applied per acre in HH farm plots in CWZ (Table 2.20). Women in CWZ did not respond to the quantities applied on their farm plots. Maybe they did not apply fertilizer at all on their plots. The very large standard deviations are indications of wide variations in the quantities of fertilizers applied (Table 2.20). It is likely commercially-oriented farmers apply far more fertilizers than those who are not market-oriented farmers. A further study of input use by different types of farmers in the zones will be useful.

Table 2.20: Fertilizer use per acre (kg/acre) in 2022 cropping season

	N		Household HH farm plots	Individual men farm plots	Individual women farm plots	Household farm holding
Central West Zone	10	Average	300.0	350.0	-	325.0
		Std. Dev.	259.80	-	-	-
		Max	850	350	-	850
		Min	100	350	-	100
North Zone	42	Average	744.4	462.5	108.3	438.4
		Std. Dev.	1077.25	296.10	72.16	481.84
		Max	4500	1000	150	4500
		Min	50	100	25	25
Total (both zones)	32	Average area	522.2	406.3	108.3	381.7
		Std. Dev.	668.53	296.10	72.16	481.84
		Max	850	350	150	850
		Min	50	100	25	25

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

2.4.3 Use of organic fertilizers

Table 2.21 indicates the importance of organic fertilizer use in the two zones of Senegal. Over 93% of the farmers use organic manure in the HH farms in both zones. It is also good to know that organic fertilizer is used by women on their individual farms in the CWZ. Organic fertilizer was not however applied to individual women farms in 2022 in the NZ (Table 2.21). It will be good to know why that is so.

Table 2.21: Organic fertilizer utilization

Farm Plots	Central West Zone				North Zone			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	15	93.8	1	6.2	21	93.5	11	6.5
Individual men farm plots	1	100.0	0	0.0	8	72.7	3	27.3
Individual women farm plots (from WiHH)	10	76.9	3	23.1	0	0.0	3	100.0
Total	26	86.7	4	13.3	29	63.0	17	37.0

CHAPTER 3

FARMING SYSTEMS BY ZONES

3.1 Crop-Based Systems

3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures

Mixed cropping is a common practice in the CWZ and the NZ . The cropping systems of the areas are captured by noting the crops and crop mixtures that are planted in the household as well as the individual men and women farm plots. Crop mixtures range from two to five or more crops. The most common crop/crop mixtures as captured by the survey for each of the zones are given in Tables 3.1 and 3.2 for NZ and CWZ respectively. The tables show how complex the cropping systems are. Crops that dominate in the mixtures in CWZ are millet, groundnuts, maize and beans (cowpea) (Table 3.1), while rice, tomatoes, onions, and okro dominate in the NZNZ (Table 3.2). The type of crops dominating the two zones is a clear indication that the zones have different agro-climatic conditions.

Table 3.1: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in households- HHH in Central West Zone

Crops/crop mixtures	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women's plots	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Millet/ Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)	5	31.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Maize/ Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)	3	18.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Sorghum/Rice/Groundnut/ Beans(Cowpea)	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/ Sorghum/ Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)/ Watermelon	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/ Rice/ Groundnut	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0
Millet/ Maize/ Groundnut/ Watermelon	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/Maize/Groundnut/Beans (Cowpea/Cassava	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/ Maize) / Groundnut	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/ Maize/ Beans (Cowpea)	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Millet/ Groundnut	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Maize/ Beans (Cowpea)	1	6.3	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Millet, groundnut, and cowpea for instance tolerate dry spells and are thus suitable for dry areas such as the CWZ (Table 3.1). On the other hand, rice, tomatoes, and onions are water-intensive crops and thus grow well in areas that are relatively muddy and water-logged, hence, their dominance in the NZ (Table 3.2). It is interesting to note that for most of the crop mixtures, especially in the CWZ, legumes such as cowpea and groundnuts are mostly mixed with cereals and/or other crops. This practice is common in dry areas of West Africa and helps to conserve soil water and nutrients.

Table 3.2: Major cropping systems (crop/crop mixtures) in households- HHH in North Zone

Crops/crop mixtures	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women plots	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Rice	8	25.0	2	18.2	2	66.7
Rice/Tomatoes	3	9.4	3	27.3	0	0.0
Groundnut	3	9.4	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cassava	3	9.4	0	0.0	0	0.0
Turnip/Beetroot/Pepper/Tomatoes/Onion	0	0.0	1	9.1	0	0.0
Tomatoes/ Onions	0	0.0	1	9.1	0	0.0
Tomatoes/ Okro/ Onions/ Mango/ Citrus (orange/ lemon/ guava/ grapes etc.)	1	3.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rice/ Turnip/ Okro/ Watermelon	1	3.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rice/ Tomatoes/ Okro/ Aubergine	1	3.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rice/ Pepper/ Tomatoes/ Okro/ Onions	1	3.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rice/Pepper/Onions/Watermelon/Melon	1	3.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Rice/ Maize/ Groundnut/ Tomatoes	1	3.1	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

The relative importance of crops to people can be partly inferred by the number of times the crops appear in the various crop/crop mixtures. Tables 3.3 and 3.4 give that information for the CWZ and NZ respectively. Groundnuts, millet, beans (cowpea), and maize are the most commonly cultivated crops in the CWZ and thus can be assumed to be the most important to household members in that zone. In the case of the SRVZ, rice, tomatoes, groundnuts, onions, and okro are the most commonly cultivated crops. The numerous types of crops grown in the NZ, especially fruits and vegetables, roots and tubers etc. is an indication of the diverse diets the people will be consuming and the likelihood of a higher diet diversity scores and better nutrition of the people.

Table 3.3: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) – Central West Zone

Crops	HH Farm Plots		Individual men farm plots		Total
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Groundnuts	14	26.4	1	33.3	15
Millet	12	22.6	1	33.3	13
Beans (Cowpea)	13	24.5	0	0	13
Maize	8	15.1	0	0	8
Sorghum	2	3.8	0	0	2
Watermelon	2	3.8	0	0	2
Rice	1	1.9	1	33.3	2
Cassava	1	1.9	0	0	1
Total	53	100.0	3	99.9	55

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.4: Relative importance of crops (number of times crops appear in crop/crop mixtures) –North Zone

Crops	HH Farm Plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Rice	19	26	5	15.6	2	50	26
Tomatoes	10	13.7	7	21.9	0	0	17
Groundnut	9	12.3	2	6.3	0	0	11
Onions	6	8.2	5	15.6	0	0	11
Okro	5	6.8	2	6.3	0	0	7
Pepper	4	5.5	2	6.3	0	0	6
Cassava	5	6.8	0	0	0	0	5
Citrus (orange, lemon, guava, grapes etc.)	2	2.7	2	6.3	0	0	4
Aubergine	2	2.7	1	3.1	1	25	4
Turnip	2	2.7	1	3.1	0	0	3
Mango	2	2.7	1	3.1	0	0	3
Frafra (Hausa) potato (<i>Solenostemon rotundifolius</i>)	0	0.0	2	6.3	0	0	2
Watermelon	2	2.7	0	0	0	0	2
Hibiscus	1	1.4	0	0	1	25	2
Maize	1	1.4	0	0	0	0	1
Beans/Cowpea	1	1.4	0	0	0	0	1
Sweet potato	0	0	1	3.1	0	0	1
Carrots	1	1.4	0	0	0	0	1
Beetroot	0	0	1	3.1	0	0	1
Melon	1	1.4	0	0	0	0	1
Total	73	99.8	32	100.1	4	100	109

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.1.2 Planting materials and sources

The types of planting materials and sources of acquisition vary from person to person in both zones. Tables 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, and 3.8 present results of the types and sources of planting materials in the CWZ and NZ . The results from both HHH and WiHH in both zones indicate that most households in the CWZ use indigenous seed from their own storage (Table 3.5), while farmers in the NZ use indigenous seed purchased from other farmers (Table 3.6). It is worth noting that relatively many WiHHs in CWZ also use improved seed (purchased), particularly in the case of vegetables such as onions, potatoes, and leafy vegetables and others (Table 3.7).

Table 3.5: Types and Sources of planting materials- Central West Zone- HHHs

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	2	1	-	0
	Improved (Open pollinated)	-	-	-	2
Rice	Rice – Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Rice	Indigenous	10	-	-	-
Millet	Indigenous	6	6	-	-
Groundnut	Indigenous	4	5	-	-
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	-	1	-	-
Soybean	Indigenous	-	-	-	1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.6: Types and Sources of planting materials- NorthZone – HHHs

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Rice	Indigenous	3	12	2	1
Groundnut	Indigenous	1	5	-	-
Cassava	Indigenous	1	4	-	-
Vegetables	Indigenous	-	8	-	-
Onion	Indigenous	-	5	-	-
	Improved	-	1	-	-
	Hybrid	-	2	-	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.7: Types and Sources of planting materials- Central West Zone- WiHHs

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Maize	Indigenous	1	-	-	0
	Improved	0	-	-	1
Rice	Indigenous	4	-	-	1
Millet	Indigenous	2	-	-	-
Groundnut	Indigenous	2	-	-	-
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	2	1	-	-
Sorghum	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
Vegetables	Indigenous	1	-	-	-
	Improved	-	-	-	2
	Hybrid	-	-	-	4
Onion	Indigenous	-	1	-	-
	Improved	-	.	-	1
	Hybrid	-	3	-	6
Potato	Indigenous	-	1	-	-
	Hybrid	-	1	-	6

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- North Zone - WiHHs

Type of seeds used		Source of seed			
		Own seed	Local seed (purchased)	Local seed (from other farmers)	Improved seed (purchased)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq
Rice	Indigenous (local)	-	7	1	1
Groundnut	Indigenous	-	2	-	-
Cassava	Indigenous	-	3	-	-
Vegetables	Indigenous	-	3	-	-
Onion	Indigenous	-	1	-	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.1.3 Soil amendment practices

The main soil amendment practices in the CWZ and NZ are crop rotation, use of manure (organic materials), use of inorganic fertilizer, and fallow lands. As shown in Table 3.9, about 40% of HHHs in the CWZ indicated that their households use manure (organic materials) as the main soil amendment, followed by crop rotation (33%) and fertilizer (13%). In the case of the NZ, 50% of HHH respondents indicated that crop rotation is the main soil amendment practice, followed by fallow lands (24%) and then organic materials (12%). The responses from WiHH (Table 3.10) are similar to the responses of HHH in both zones, confirming the use of organic materials and crop rotation as the main soil amendment practices in the zones. This may be an indication of the possibility of success of agroecological practices in the area since most practices are indigenous and depend on resources that are available locally.

Table 3.9: Soil amendment practices in households- HHH

Soil amendment practices	Central West Zone		NorthZone	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	5	33.3	17	50.0
Use of manure (organic materials)	6	40.0	4	11.8
Use of inorganic fertilizer	2	13.3	2	5.9
Land fallow	-	-	8	23.5
Others	2	13.3	3	8.8
Total	15	100.0	34	100.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.10: Soil amendment practices in households- WiHH

Soil amendment practices	Central West Zone		NorthZone	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	4	26.7	14	73.7
Use of manure (organic materials)	9	60.0	3	15.8
Use of fertilizer	-	-	1	5.3
Land fallow	-	-	1	5.3
Others	2	13.3		
Total	15	100.0	19	100.0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

3.1.4 Crop production constraints

Crop production can face various constraints that impact agricultural productivity. These constraints may differ by gender and/or agroecological zones. A method of **weighted scores of ranked frequencies² (WSRF)** was used to obtain percentage weighted scores to determine the relative importance of farmers' crop constraints from their perspective. Respondents were asked to identify five main crop production constraints and rank them 1 to 5, 1 being the most severe and 5 the least. The frequencies of the ranks were then weighted and percentage scores computed (see Appendix 1). The method is a more robust way of ranking the constraints. It is important to understand variations in priorities and constraints to be able to devise effective interventions to promote sustainable food systems. The results are given in Figures 3.1 and 3.2 for HHHs and WiHHs respectively. In the CWZ, the first three most significant constraints for HHHs are erratic rainfall, finance, soil fertility, and pests and diseases. And for the NZ, they are, access to production inputs, pests and diseases, soil fertility, and finance (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 Relative importance of crop production constraints according to HHHs in CWZ and NZ

During focus group discussion, the HHHs added that the main constraints that local farmers face are the problems of selling agricultural products, the lack of quality seeds especially for sorghum, the lack of alternatives to the use of chemical fertilizers, delays in subsidized agricultural inputs, inadequacy of agricultural tools, and land degradation due to continuous cultivation. For those who cultivate rice in the dry season (under irrigation), they noted that there is total lack of security in their fields. This is why even before harvesting, the livestock herds begin to ravage the rice fields, which is the origin of several conflicts.

² See Appendix 1 for details of the method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies (WSRF).

For the women (WiHHs), finance, erratic rainfall, and access to production inputs are the main crop production constraints in the CWZ. For the NZ, the main crop production constraints are related to access to farming land, access to production inputs, and finance (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Relative importance of crop production constraints according to WiHHs zones

While women in both the CWZ and the NZ share common concerns regarding finance and access to production inputs, regional variations exist, with differences in the specific constraints identified. Understanding these differences is crucial for tailoring interventions and support mechanisms to address the unique needs of women farmers in each zone. In the CWZ, women identify erratic rainfall as a major constraint, whereas in the NZ, access to farming land is noted as a primary challenge. This suggests differing environmental and geographical factors influencing crop production in each zone. Additionally, the order of constraints varies between the two zones, with finance listed first for women in the CWZ, whereas access to farming land is prioritized for the NZ.

3.2 Livestock-Based Systems

3.2.1 Animal ownership and management

Livestock-based systems play a crucial role in sustaining rural livelihoods and ensuring food security in the CWZ and the NZ. Understanding the dynamics of animal ownership and management by gender in specific zones is essential for informed agricultural development. Tables 3.11, 3.12, 3.13, and 3.14 provide distinct practices of animal ownership and management in the CWZ and the NZ, with a focus on men (household heads) and women.

In the CWZ, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023. These included large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, non-ruminants such as donkeys, horses, and pigs, as well as poultry consisting of fowls (chickens), guinea fowls, and turkeys (Table 3.11).

Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Central West Zone for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	3.6	2.70	1.8	0.96	3.4	4.83	0.5	0.71
Donkeys	1.0	-	0.0	-	1.0	-	0.0	-
Horse	2.2	1.55	0.0	-	2.2	1.55	0.0	-
Sheep	8.4	3.50	2.0	1.48	5.6	1.57	0.8	0.84
Goats	1.6	5.00	1.0	1.16	5.0	1.63	0.0	-
Pigs	16.3	4.35	6.8	2.22	8.5	3.87	2.0	1.00
Fowls (Chickens)	28.4	21.0	2.0	2.00	14.6	10.13	1.0	1.73
Guinea fowls	0.0	-	0.0	-	2.0	-	0.0	-
Turkey	21.0	-	6.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 4, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 3. By 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 3, with an SD of 5. Sheep ownership averaged 8 in 2022, with a standard deviation of 3.5, while goats averaged 2. For non-ruminants like donkeys, horses, and pigs, the average owned in 2022 is 1, 2, and 16 respectively. In 2023, average sheep ownership decreased to 6, while goat ownership increased to 5. Average ownership of donkeys and horses remained constant in 2023, while average pig ownership decreased to 9. Fowls and turkey ownership averaged 28 and 21, respectively, in 2022. In 2023, fowl and turkey ownership declined, and the average guinea fowl ownership was 2. In terms of the sale of livestock by household heads, there is consistency in the sale of cattle, sheep, and pigs in 2022 and 2023. m

Between 2022 and 2023, cattle ownership declined from 4 to 3, signaling reduced ownership among men in the CWZ. Sheep ownership decreased from 8 to 6, while goat ownership rose from 2 to 5, reflecting a preference shift. Pig ownership notably dropped from 16 to 9. Despite fewer sales in 2023, consistency prevailed in cattle, sheep, and pig sales, indicating a stable market.

Similar to the men in the household, women in the household owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, non-ruminants like donkeys, horses, and pigs, and poultry including fowls (chickens), guinea fowls, and ducks (Table 3.12).

Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Central West Zone for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	3.3	2.66	1.3	1.51	3.2	4.36	0.0	-
Donkeys	1.0	-	0.0	-	1.0	-	0.0	-
Horse	2.0	1.53	0.0	-	2.0	1.53	0.0	-
Sheep	7.9	3.57	2.0	1.63	5.3	1.77	0.8	0.96
Goats	5.7	4.04	0.7	1.16	2.8	1.50	0.0	-
Pigs	16.3	4.35	6.8	2.22	8.5	3.87	1.8	0.96
Fowls (Chickens)	27.4	15.37	8.0	10.58	11.8	7.13	7.0	9.90
Guinea fowls	0.0	-	0.0	-	2.0.0	-	0.0	-
Duck	21.0	-	6.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In 2022, women in the CWZ owned an average of 3 cattle, with approximately 1 sold. By 2023, no sales were reported for cattle. Sheep and goat ownership averaged 8 and 6, while non-ruminants—donkeys, horses, and pigs—averaged 1, 2, and 16, respectively, in 2022. Sales were recorded for sheep, goats, and pigs in 2022. In 2023, sheep and goat ownership decreased to 5 and 3, respectively, while donkey and horse ownership remained constant. Goats had no sales in 2023, and sales declined for sheep and pigs. Average pig ownership declined in 2023. Fowl (chicken) and duck ownership averaged 27 and 21, respectively, in 2022. In 2023, average fowl and duck ownership decreased, with women owning an average of 2 guinea fowls. The average number of chickens sold was 8 and 7 in 2022 and 2023, respectively, while ducks sold 6 in 2022 but none in 2023.

There are distinct patterns in livestock ownership and management practices between men and women in the CWZ. Women tend to own fewer livestock than men, do, particularly in cattle, and non-ruminants. However, women showed more stability in their ownership patterns over the two years, with slight declines in some areas, while men exhibited greater variability, particularly in cattle and pig ownership.

In the NZ, householdheads (men) owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, pigs, and poultry consisting of fowls (chickens), and guinea fowls (Table 3.13).

Table 3.13: Men livestock ownership and sales in the North Zone for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	12.6	14.24	3.6	6.00	16.0	23.11	3.56	8.07
Donkeys	2.5	2.12	0.0	-	2.5	2.12	0.0	-
Sheep	4.5	2.20	2.1	5.04	2.5	1.69	0.6	0.74
Goats	3.0	-	0.0	-	2.0	-	0.0	-
Horse	2.5	2.12	0.0	-	2.5	2.12	0.0	-
Fowls (Chickens)	149.0	275.24	128.0	264.42	81.0	135.53	68.0	130.84

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 12, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 14. By 2023, the average cattle ownership increased to 16, with an SD of 23. Donkey, horse, and goats' ownership averaged 3 each in 2022, while sheep also averaged 5. In 2023, while the average number of donkeys and horses owned remained constant, the average number of sheep owned declined to 3, and goat ownership also decreased to 2. Fowl ownership averaged 149 in 2022; however, in 2023, fowl ownership decreased to 81. In terms of the sale of livestock, the average number of cattle, sheep, and fowls sold declined between 2022 and 2023, while donkeys, horses, and goats experienced no sales in either year. Overall, Table 3.13 suggests an increase in cattle ownership among men in the NZ from 2022 to 2023, along with fluctuations and declines in the ownership and sale of other livestock species.

In 2022 and 2023, women owned various types of livestock, including cattle, sheep, goats, and fowls (chickens) (Table 3.14).

Table 3.14: Women livestock ownership and sales in the NorthZone for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	6.0	-	4.0	-	6.0	-	4.0	-
Sheep	3.8	1.42	0.3	0.63	1.4	1.19	0.2	0.44
Goats	2.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	-
Fowls (Chickens)	8.5	0.71	4.0	5.66	3.0	-	0.0	-

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In 2022, the average number of cattle owned by women in the NZ was 6, with an average of 4 sold. By 2023, the average cattle ownership remained constant, as did the sales. Among women in households in the NZ, sheep and goat ownership averaged 4 and 2, respectively, in 2022, with basically nosheep sold. In 2023, both sheep and goat ownership declined, and sheep sales

decreased, while goats received no sales for 2022 and 2023. The average ownership of fowl (chickens) for women was 9 in 2022, with an average of 4 sales. In 2023, fowl ownership decreased to 3 with no sales.

Clear patterns emerge in livestock ownership and management practices between men and women in the NZ. Both genders experienced stability in cattle ownership and sales from 2022 to 2023. However, there was a decline in sheep and goat ownership among both men and women, leading to reductions in sales. Additionally, fowl ownership and sales decreased for both genders during the same period. Men generally had higher average cattle ownership compared to women throughout the observed years. While fluctuations in ownership and sales were observed for both genders, men tended to exhibit larger variations in cattle and fowl ownership compared to women. Notably, sheep sales decreased for women, while men experienced a decline in sheep ownership.

In the CWZ, women owned fewer livestock compared to men, particularly in cattle, non-ruminants, and poultry. Women demonstrated more stable ownership patterns with slight declines, while men exhibited greater variability, especially in cattle and pig ownership over the two years. In the NZ, both men and women experienced stable cattle ownership and sales from 2022 to 2023. However, sheep and goat ownership declined for both genders, resulting in reduced sales. Similarly, fowl ownership and sales decreased for both groups. Men generally maintained higher average cattle ownership than women, with larger variations in cattle and fowl ownership. Sheep sales decreased for women, and men saw a decline in sheep ownership.

3.2.2 Animal breeds, sources, and characteristics

Animal breeds

Animal breeds may vary based on geographical locations and gender-specific practices. The livestock breeds commonly reared by men in the CWZ and NZ are indigenous or local breeds (Tables 3.5). For cattle, goats, donkeys, sheep, and horse breeds, men mostly rear indigenous or local breeds in both the CWZ and the NZ. However, for pigs and fowl (chickens), men rear crossbred or exotic breeds in addition to the indigenous breeds in the CWZ.

Tables 3.15: Livestock breeds reared by men in Central West Zone and North Zone

Type breeds reared		Central West Zone		NorthZone	
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cattle	Indigenous (local)	5	100.0	14	73.7
	Crossbred	0	0.0	4	21.1
	Exotic	0	0.0	1	5.3
Goats	Indigenous	4	100.0	4	100.0
Pigs	Indigenous	1	25.0	0	0.0
	Crossbred	3	75.0	0	0.0
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	6	85.7	6	100.0
	Crossbred	1	14.3	0	0.0
Donkeys	Indigenous	2	100.0	6	100.0
Sheep	Indigenous	9	81.8	9	100.0
	Crossbred	2	18.2	0	0.0
Horse	Indigenous	11	100.0	5	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

The livestock breeds commonly reared by women in the CWZ and NZ did not differ, mostly indigenous or local breeds (Tables 3.16). For cattle, goats, donkeys, and horse breeds, women mostly reared indigenous or local breeds in both the CWZ and the NZ. However, for pigs, sheep, and fowl (chickens), women reared crossbred or exotic breeds in addition to the indigenous breeds in the CWZ.

Tables 3.16: Livestock breeds reared by women in Central West Zone and North Zone

Type breeds reared		Central West Zone		NorthZone	
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cattle	Indigenous (local)	5	100.0	1	100.0
Goats	Indigenous	4	100.0	2	100.0
Pigs	Indigenous	1	25.0	0	0.0
	Crossbred	3	75.0	0	0.0
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	7	87.5	2	100.0
	Crossbred	1	12.5	0	0.0
Donkeys	Indigenous	2	100.0	1	100.0
Sheep	Indigenous	8	80.0	12	100.0
	Crossbred	1	10.0	0	0.0
	Exotic	1	10.0	0	0.0
Horse	Indigenous	8	100.0	1	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

While there is significant overlap in the types of livestock breeds reared by men and women, distinctions are evident, particularly in the CWZ, regarding the additional rearing of crossbred or exotic breeds by both men and women for certain animals like pigs and fowl.

Sources of Animal breeds

The main source from which the animals are obtained varies based on the type of animal and gender (Tables 3.17 and 3.18). In the CWZ, Table 3.17 shows that most household heads purchase cattle (100%), donkeys (100%), horses (91%), fowls (71%), pigs (100%), and sheep (82%) breeds locally. Few breeds of horses, fowls (chickens), and sheep are owned by the household heads. Compared to women in households, while some breeds of fowls and sheep are purchased locally, other breeds of the same livestock types, albeit fewer, are purchased from exotic sources. Similar to men, goat breeds are mostly owned or purchased locally by women.

Table 3.17 Men and Women main source of animal breeds in Central West Zone

Animal	Exotic(purchased)		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Household head (men)						
Cattle	0	0.0	5	100.0	0	0.0
Donkeys	0	0.0	2	100.0	0	0.0
Horse	0	0.0	10	90.9	1	9.1
Fowls (chickens)	0	0.0	5	71.4	2	28.6
Goats	0	0.0	1	25.0	3	75.0
Guinea fowls	0	0.0	2	100.0	0	0.0
Sheep	0	0.0	9	81.8	1	9.1
Pigs	0	0.0	4	100.0	0	0.0
Cattle	0	0.0	5	100.0	0	0.0
Donkeys	0	0.0	2	100.0	0	0.0
Horse	0	0.0	7	87.5	1	12.5
Fowls (chickens)	1	12.5	6	75.0	1	12.5
Goats	0	0.0	2	50.0	2	50.0
Guinea fowls	0	0.0	2	100.0	0	0.0
Sheep	1	10.0	9	90.0	0	0.0
Pigs	0	0.0	4	100.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the NZ, Table 3.18 indicates that all indigenous breeds of fowls (chickens), horses, and sheep are purchased locally by household heads. Goats and donkeys, mostly purchased locally by household heads, are also owned by them. The sources for cattle breeds by household heads are diverse. While about 79% are purchased locally, 11% are purchased as exotic breeds, while 5% each are either given by other farmers or owned by the household head. There is a sharp contrast for the women in households in terms of the sources of livestock breeds. All women in the NZ purchase livestock locally.

Table 3.18 Main source of animal breeds in the North Zone

Animal	Exotic-purchased		Local - given by other farmers		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Household heads (men)								
Cattle	2	10.5	1	5.3	15	78.9	1	5.3
Donkeys	0	0.0	0	0.0	5	83.3	1	16.7
Horse	0	0.0	0	0.0	5	100.0	0	0.0
Fowls (chickens)	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	100.0	0	0.0
Goats	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	50.0	2	50.0
Sheep	0	0.0	0	0.0	9	100.0	0	0.0
Women in household								
Cattle	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0
Donkeys	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0
Horse	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0
Fowls (chickens)	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	100.0	0	0.0
Goats	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	100.0	0	0.0
Sheep	0	0.0	0	0.0	12	100.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

While both zones exhibit a preference for local purchases for certain livestock breeds, there are notable differences in the sources of breeds, particularly regarding the prevalence of local purchases and exotic sources, as well as the involvement of women in owning or purchasing goat breeds, which is specific to the CWZ. In the CWZ, there is a mix of locally purchased breeds and breeds from exotic sources for fowls and sheep, while in the NZ, , all livestock breeds are purchased locally by household heads. Goat breeds are mostly owned or purchased locally by women in the CWZ, whereas in the NZ , goat breeds are also purchased locally.

Special characteristics of animal breeds

Animal breeds exhibit unique traits or features that set one breed apart from another. Tables 3.19 and 3.20 showcase the distinct characteristics of animals for men and women in the CWZ and the NZ In the CWZ, the majority of household heads indicated that cattle breeds are known for being highly productive in terms of meat and milk, producing a lot of manure, and being easily available (Table 3.19). Additionally, for the household heads, donkeys, horses, sheep, goats, pigs, fowls (chickens), and guinea fowls, apart from being productive, are also easily available, which is a special characteristic of the breeds reared in CWZ.

Table 3.19: Special characteristics of animal breeds in Central West Zone

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg)		Hardy (resilient in the environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads												
Cattle	5	35.7	0	0.0	1	7.1	1	7.1	3	21.4	4	28.6
Donkeys	0	0.0	2	28.6	1	14.3	0	0.0	2	28.6	2	28.6
Horse	2	6.7	9	30.0	3	10.0	0	0.0	8	26.7	8	26.7
Sheep	8	21.6	5	13.5	1	2.7	6	16.2	8	21.6	9	24.3
Goats	2	20.0	1	10.0	2	20.0	1	10.0	3	30.0	1	10.0
Pigs	4	26.7	1	6.7	0	0.0	3	20.0	3	20.0	4	26.7
Fowls (Chickens)	6	35.3	1	5.9	1	5.9	3	17.6	6	35.3	0	0.0
Guinea fowls	2	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	25.0	1	25.0
Women in households												
Cattle	4	30.8	0	0.0	1	7.7	1	7.7	3	23.1	4	30.8
Donkeys	0	0	2	50.0	1	25.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	25.0
Horse	0	0	7	35.0	2	10.0	0	0.0	5	25.0	6	30.0
Sheep	10	30.3	4	12.1	1	3.0	1	3.0	8	24.2	9	27.3
Goats	2	18.2	3	27.3	1	9.1	0	0.0	4	36.4	1	9.1
Pigs	4	26.7	1	6.7	1	6.7	2	13.3	3	20.0	4	26.7
Fowls (Chickens)	6	30	2	10.0	0	0.0	4	20.0	7	35.0	1	5.0
Guinea fowls	2	33.3	0	0.0	1	16.7	1	16.7	2	33.3	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For the women in CWZ, the majority of them attribute special characteristics to cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, fowls, and guinea fowls, noting their high productivity level, and easy availability. Few other women in the household characterise cattle, sheep, pigs, fowls (Chickens) and guinea fowls for their good taste. Specifically for cattle, sheep, and pigs, more than 20% indicate their ability to produce lots of manure.

Overall, while both household heads and women in the CWZ recognize the productivity and availability of various animal breeds, women also place importance on taste, and a significant portion highlights the manure production capacity of certain animals.

In the NZ, the majority of household heads indicated that cattle breeds are known for good taste (22%), producing a lot of manure (21%), hardy (18%), highly productive in terms of meat and milk (16%), and disease resistant (8%) (Table 3.20). Goats also share similar characteristics as cattle, while no household head mentioned fowls as disease-resistant in the NZ.

Table 3.20: Special characteristics of animal breeds in NorthZone

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg, etc)		Hardy (resilient in the environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cattle	13	15.7	15	18.1	7	8.4	18	21.7	13	15.7	17	20.5
Donkeys	0	0.0	3	25	2	16.7	0	0.0	3	25.0	4	33.3
Horse	0	0.0	3	23.1	3	23.1	0	0.0	4	30.8	3	23.1
Sheep	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	11.1	0	0.0	5	55.6	3	33.3
Goats	2	18.2	2	18.2	2	18.2	2	18.2	2	18.2	1	9.1
Fowls (Chickens)	3	18.8	3	18.8	0	0.0	3	18.8	4	25.0	3	18.8
Cattle	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Donkeys	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0
Horse	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0
Sheep	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	8.3	0	0.0	9	75.0	2	16.7
Goats	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Fowls (Chickens)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	1	50.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Women in the NZ attributed special characteristics to sheep noting their availability, potential to produce manure, and disease resistance (Table 3.20). For the women, availability was a special characteristic ascribed to donkeys, horses, sheep, and fowls. They also mentioned sheep, goats, and fowls (Chickens) to produce ample manure.

Overall, while household heads and women in the NZ recognize various characteristics of different animal breeds, there are differences in their specific perceptions. Household heads focus on attributes like taste, manure production, hardiness, productivity, and disease resistance, while women highlight ease of availability and disease resistance in sheep, as well as the manure production capacity of several animals. Additionally, household heads do not mention fowls as being disease-resistant, while women do not emphasize the hardiness of cattle.

3.2.3 Livestock constraints

Livestock production encounters diverse constraints that may affect its efficiency, with variations observed across zones, genders, and types of livestock, including large ruminants (e.g., cattle), small ruminants (e.g., goats and sheep), and poultry (e.g., chickens). Figures 3.3 to 3.10 illustrate the distinct types of livestock and the constraints experienced by household

heads (men) and women in the CWZ and NZ. The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies was used to obtain the relative importance of the constraints to both men (HHHs) and women (WiHHs).

Cattle production constraints

Figures 3.3 and 3.4 illustrate the constraints on cattle production for household heads (men) and women in the CWZ and NZ . The constraints identified among men in both zones include lack of feed during the dry season, diseases, limited access to information on livestock management, access to veterinary services, and inadequate housing (Figure 3.3). While these constraints, particularly the scarcity of feed during the dry season, diseases, access to information on livestock management, and veterinary services, are more pronounced in the CWZ, there is consistency in the challenges faced by men in both zones regarding cattle production. However, there are specific constraints unique to household heads in the CWZ, such as the lack of time to care for cattle, whereas, in the NZ , theft of cattle is a distinct concern among household heads.

Figure 3.3 HHHs cattle production constraints by zones

The constraints on cattle production for women in the CWZ and NZ include the lack of feed during the dry season, diseases, and poor housing (Figure 3.4). While there are common constraints between the two zones, women in households also reported other constraints that appear to be unique to each zone. Among the common constraints, a higher percentage of women in households in the CWZ reported lack of feed during the dry season (50%), cattle diseases (30%), and limited access to information on livestock management (10%), compared to those in the NZ , where the percentages were 33%, 15%, and 2%, respectively. Poor housing was identified as a more significant constraint in the NZ (24%) compared to the CWZ(10%). Additionally, the constraints peculiar to the NZ include theft (24%) and lack of water during the dry season (2%).

Figure 3.4 WiHHs cattle production constraints by zone

While both household heads and women in households face common challenges in cattle production, such as lack of feed, diseases, and limited access to resources and services, there are also distinct constraints specific to each group and zone. For instance, household heads (men) in the CWZ face unique challenges, such as the lack of time to care for cattle, while household heads in the NZ deal with the significant concern of cattle theft. Poor housing is identified as a more significant constraint for women in households in the NZ compared to those in the CWZ. Additionally, unique constraints for women in the NZ include theft and lack of water during the dry season.

Goat production constraints

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 depict the goat production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the CWZ and NZ. In the CWZ, men's constraints in goat production include lack of feed during the dry season, diseases, theft, animal attacks, and limited access to grazing. Meanwhile, in the NZ men's constraints primarily involve a lack of feed during the dry season and animal attacks (Figure 3.5). Although the constraints for men may be similar in both zones, the percentage of household heads reporting these constraints is higher in the NZ, particularly concerning theft and animal attacks. Notably, during Focus Group Discussions, it was reported that goats are particularly vulnerable to dog attacks in Senegal in general, but this issue is more pronounced in the NZ.

Figure 3.5 Goat production constraints by zone (Household head)

For women in the CWZ and the NZ, the goat production constraints mentioned by the women in households are shown in Figure 3.6. In both zones, there are similar constraints as well as isolated ones. In the CWZ, diseases (33%) were the most pressing constraint, while in the NZ, 17% of the women in households indicated diseases. Conversely, 33% of the women indicated theft and a lack of feed in the dry season as constraints in goat production in the NZ compared to the CWZ with 22% and 11%, respectively. Regarding isolated goat production constraints, about 11% each mentioned poor housing and a lack of market as constraints in the CWZ.

Figure 3.6 Goat production constraints by Zone (Women)

While there are commonalities in the constraints faced by household heads (men) and women in both zones, such as a lack of feed during the dry season and diseases, women, particularly

in the NZ , are more affected by theft and a lack of feed during the dry season compared to household heads. While diseases are a significant constraint for both household heads and women in the CWZ, theft, and a lack of feed during the dry season emerge as more pressing concerns for both groups in the NZ . Household heads tend to report a broader range of constraints, including those related to property protection (theft) and environmental factors (animal attacks), whereas women may prioritize constraints that directly affect the well-being and productivity of the goats they manage, such as diseases and feed availability.

Sheep production constraints

Figures 3.7 and 3.8 depict the sheep production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the CWZ and the NZ . In the CWZ, the most pressing sheep production constraints for men include a lack of feed during the dry season (38%), theft (38%), limited access to veterinary services (27%), diseases (27%), as well as a lack of market (19%) and access to information on livestock management (19%). Compared to the NZ , where the percentages are as follows: a lack of feed during the dry season (11%), theft (11%), access to veterinary services (29%), diseases (29%), lack of market (2%), and access to information on livestock management (2%) (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7 Sheep production constraints by zone(household head)

For women (Figure 3.8), the most pressing sheep production constraints in the CWZ are lack of feed in the dry season, diseases, access to information on livestock management, theft, poor housing, and access to veterinary services, in order of priority. In the NZ , the constraints for women are related to diseases, access to veterinary services, lack of feed during the dry season, and limited access to livestock management information.

Figure 3.8 Sheep production constraints by zone(women)

While there are common constraints faced by both men and women in sheep production across both zones, there are also notable differences in priority. Men in both zones predominantly face issues related to theft and limited access to veterinary services, suggesting a concern for the protection and health management of their sheep. Women, on the other hand, highlight constraints such as poor housing and limited access to information on livestock management, indicating a broader range of responsibilities beyond direct production concerns. The NZ presents unique constraints, with women specifically noting limited access to livestock management information as a constraint, which may indicate disparities in educational opportunities or information dissemination in this region. Access to markets emerges as a more significant concern for women in the CWZ compared to the NZ, indicating potential differences in economic opportunities and infrastructure between the two zones.

Fowls (chicken) production constraints

Figures 3.9 and 3.10 show the fowl (chicken) production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the CWZ and NZ, respectively. In the CWZ, men's most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints are diseases (62%), lack of feed during the dry season (15%), and access to information on livestock management (15%), with theft accounting for 8%. In the NZ, the constraints for men are similar to those in the CWZ, but diseases (23%) and access to veterinary services (23%) are ranked as major constraints. Additionally, access to veterinary services, lack of market, and financing emerge as unique constraints for men in the NZ (Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.9 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by zone

For women in the household as shown in Figure 3.10, the most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints in both the CWZ and the NZ are diseases and access to veterinary services. In the CWZ, disease is the leading constraint for women in fowl (chicken) production compared to the NZ. Lack of market, access to information on livestock management, and animal attacks are unique constraints in the CWZ, whereas theft is a specific constraint in the NZ (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10 Fowl (chicken) production constraints by zone(women)

While there are commonalities in fowl production constraints faced by men and women across both regions, there are also notable differences in priority. Diseases are a common concern for women in both regions; however, the CWZ places a higher emphasis on disease as the leading constraint for women in fowl production compared to the NZ. This suggests potential variations in disease prevalence or management strategies between the two regions. Women in the CWZ face unique constraints such as a lack of market, limited access to information on livestock management, and animal attacks, indicating a broader range of challenges beyond disease management compared to their counterparts in the NZ. Theft emerges as a specific constraint for women in the NZ, indicating potential security concerns or economic

vulnerabilities specific to this zone. The general livestock constraints are confirmed during the focus group discussion, with diseases causing several animal losses. Additionally, the lack of food in the dry season, the presence of wild animals, and poor access to trees for animal food were noted.

3.3 Irrigation Farming Systems

3.3.1 Irrigation types, crops cultivated, and soil amendments.

Smallholder surface water and smallholder groundwater irrigation using diesel and petrol pumps, buckets and jerry cans and solar pumps are the main irrigation types in the CWZ as well as the NZ (Table 3.21). The use of solar pumps is mainly in the CWZ (63.6%) while smallholder surface water irrigation (using rivers and streams and the lake Guiers- diesel and petrol pumps) is the main irrigation type in the NZ (52.4%). Mechanized drip irrigation is also gradually becoming common in the NZ (14.3%). Vegetables, potatoes (sweet potato and Irish potato), and fruits are the main crops grown in the CWZ while rice, vegetables, and groundnuts are the main crops grown in the NZ (Table 3.22).

Table 3.21: Types of irrigation undertaken

Type of Irrigation undertaken	Central West Zone		NorthZone	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Smallholder surface water irrigation (using rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps	2	18.2	11	52.4
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	2	18.2	1	4.8
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Diesel and petrol pumps	0	0	2	9.5
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	7	63.6	1	4.8
Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	0	0	3	14.3
Dams and canal systems – Gravity flow (large dams)	0	0	1	4.8
Other	0	0	2	9.5
Total	11	100.0	21	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 3.22: Crops grown under irrigation.

Type of crops Irrigated	Central West Zone		Type of crops Irrigated	North Zone	
	Freq	% Freq		Freq	% Freq
Sweet potato	1	1.7	Rice	13	22.0
Potato (English/Irish)	6	10.3	Maize	1	1.7
Turnip	1	1.7	Groundnut	5	8.5
Leafy vegetables (local)	2	3.4	Sweet potato	1	1.7
Pepper	9	15.5	Carrots	1	1.7
Tomatoes	9	15.5	Turnip	2	3.4
Okro	9	15.5	Leafy vegetables (local)	2	3.4
Onions	11	19.0	Pepper	3	5.1
Mango	1	1.7	Tomatoes	11	18.6
Pawpaw/Papaye	3	5.2	Okro	6	10.2
Citrus (orange, lemon, guava, grapes etc.)	6	10.3	Onions	11	18.6
			Aubergine	3	5.1
Total	58	99.8		56	94.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

With regards to soil amendments in irrigated agriculture, the irrigators lean towards the use of organic fertilizers. They either use the organic fertilizer alone or mix it with inorganic fertilizer (Table 3.23). These practices point to a potential for the promotion of agroecological practices.

Table 3.23 Types of Soil Amendments Used.

Zone	Type of Irrigation	Type of Soil Amendments		
		Only organic fertilizers	Only inorganic fertilizers	Inorganic and organic fertilizers
		Freq	Freq	Freq
Central West Zone	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	1	0	1
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Diesel and petrol pumps	1	0	0
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	3	0	4
NorthZone	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	0	0	1
	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps	3	1	7
	Dams and canal systems – Gravity flow (large dams)	0	1	0
	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	0	0	3
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Diesel and petrol pumps	1	0	1
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	0	0	1
	Other	0	1	1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

3.3.2 Perceived success of irrigation types and irrigation constraints

The most successful type of irrigation in CWZ, according to the farmers is smallholder groundwater (GW) using solar pumps. In the NZ, smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams – using diesel and petrol pumps) and drip irrigation are the most successful (Table 3.24).

Table 3.24: Perceived level of success of different irrigation types

Zone	Type of Irrigation	Degree of Success			
		Poor (No success)	Somehow successful	Successful (Ok)	Very successful
		Freq.	Freq	Freq	Freq
Central West Zone	Smallholder groundwater (GW) irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	0	0	0	2
	Smallholder GW irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Diesel and petrol pumps	0	0	0	2
	Smallholder GW irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar	0	0	4	3
North Zone	Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps	0	7	2	2
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch	0	0	0	1
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Diesel and petrol pumps	0	0	1	1
	Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Solar pumps	0	0	1	0
	Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)	0	0	1	2
	Dams and canal systems – gravity flow (large dams)	0	0	1	0
	Other	0	0	1	1

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

As indicated in Table 3.25, the three most important irrigation constraints in the two zones are:

- 1) High cost of production inputs (seeds, fertilizers etc.)
- 2) Poor access to the inputs
- 3) Water shortages

These are the constraints (among others) that any intervention in irrigated agriculture should endeavour to tackle.

Table 3.25: Irrigation constraints

Zone	Type of Irrigation	Constraints	Freq	% Freq
Central West Zone	All types	High costs of inputs	8	40.7
		Water shortages	9	34.6
		Other (specify)	2	7.7
		Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	6	23.1
		Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	1	3.8
			26	100.0
NZ	All types	Poor access to irrigated land	1	3.1
		Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	10	31.3
		High costs of inputs	11	34.4
		Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce	3	9.4
		Water shortages	6	18.8
		Other (specify)	1	3.1
			32	100.0

Chapter 4

OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS

4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources

4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale

Income from crops

The nature of small farming activities in the study area makes it difficult to adequately estimate household income. As seen in Tables 3.1 and 3.2, most plots consist of crop mixtures, ranging from two to as many as six. To comprehensively estimate the income from a plot the value of all the crops harvested in the plot must be determined. Such information is difficult to obtain from farmers through recall interviews. Attempts were, however, made to obtain some idea of the income earned from arable crop farming, which is the main occupation of most household members in the study area, by estimating the value of two main crops in crop mixture plots in each of the plots. In the case of sole crop plots, the value of the sole crop is estimated. It is the total harvested quantity that is valued. The prices are those the farmers gave at the time of the interviews. This explanation is to indicate that caution is required in concluding the results since changes, even small changes, in prices and quantities harvested can give drastically different results. Also, what is presented in each case is gross income and not gross margin. Cost of production was not estimated because such information from recall by small farmers is not reliable and will not serve much purpose in this study. Income from livestock production was also not estimated for the same reason of unreliability of the information given by farmers. Table 4.1 gives the procedure and formula used for the estimation of household crop income.

Table 4.1: Method of estimation of household income of harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		Total quantity harvested (in local units)		Price per unit (local currency)		Value of output (local currency)
					P_{A1}	P_{B1}	
1	A1	B1	Q_{A1}	Q_{B1}	P_{A1}	P_{B1}	$(Q_{A1} \times P_{A1}) + (Q_{B1} \times P_{B1})$
2.	A2	B2	Q_{A2}	Q_{B2}	P_{A2}	P_{B2}	$(Q_{A2} \times P_{A2}) + (Q_{B2} \times P_{B2})$
etc	A_i	B_i	Q_{A_i}	Q_{B_i}	P_{A_i}	P_{B_i}	$(Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i})$
Equation for computation of the estimated household income from harvested crops (where n = number of household plots)							N $\sum_{i=1}^n ((Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i}))$
<p>A_1 = crop A from plot 1; Q_{A1} = A1 harvested quantity; P_{A1} = Price of A1 B_1 = crop B from plot 1; Q_{B1} = B1 harvested quantity; P_{B1} = Price of B1 Thus: A_i = Crop A from plot i; Q_{A_i} = A_i harvested quantity; P_{A_i} = Price of A_i etc.</p>							

Table 4.2 gives the estimated average annual incomes obtained by households from crops (using the equation given in Table 4.1)³. It is the value of harvested produce and not quantities sold that have used in the calculation. On average, households' crop produce (HHH) was worth 739,388.89 CFA Franc (1,125.40 Euros) in the CWZ and 21,177,738.89 CFA Franc (32,234.00 Euros) in NZ . The difference is so much that there is a need for further intoragation of what is responsible for the difference. There are likely to be a few large scale farmers mixed with small farmers. Disaggregated analysis may be required to understand the situation better. In the case of the women in CWZ and NZ , they obtained an average income of 1,157,166.67 CFA Franc (about 1,761.29 Euros) and 2,018,125.00 respectively from their crop farms. The divergence of income between the zones though large is much better that the case of the HHHs. A surprise result however is that the average income from the crop farms of the women in CWZ is higher than that from the household farms (which are cultivated by the HHHs). That is quite abnormal.

The Euro equivalentents are as given in Table 4.2. Except for the HHHs' income of about 17,000 Euros per year, the others are very much on the low side especially as the values are gross incomes. Costs of production could even be more than the income. This means good costs-benefit analysis (using panel data obtained over the production period) is important.

Table 4.2: Value of crop output per household* (HHH and WiHH)

Regions	Value of harvested crops per HH (HHH) in 2022 season (CFA Franc)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 657 CFA Franc)	Value of harvested crops per HH (WiHH) (women) in 2022 season (CFA Franc)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 657 CFA Franc)
Central West Zone	739,388.89	1,125.40	1,157,166.67	1,761.29
North Zone	21,177,738.89	32,234.00	2,018,125.00	3,071.73
Both Zones (income per HH)	10,958,563.89	16,679.70	1,587,645.84	2,416.51

*See Appendix 2 for details of crop output value estimations.

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Relative quantities normally consumed and sold

Besides selling household produce for income, households in the study area also consume some of their farm produce and also share some with relatives and friends. Table 4.3 indicates that HHHs and WiHHs in CWZ usually allocate about 60% and 70% respectively of their produce for home consumption and other home uses. In the NZ the proportion for home consumption and use is about 14% and 8% respectively for HHHs and WiHHs. As a result, while the proportion of quantities sold is between 20% and 26% in CWZ, they are 83% and 90% in NZ . There are significant spatial and gender differences in behaviour in CWZ and NZ at the

³ See Appendix 2 for details of crop output estimations.

household levels. It would be wrong to make any generalizations with regards to any kind of interventions in the two zones.

Table 4.3: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold according men and women in the Zones

Item	Central West Zone		NorthZone	
	HHH (men) Mean (Std. Dev.)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std. Dev.)	HHH (men) Mean (Std Dev)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std Dev.)
Proportion (%) normally left for home consumption and other home uses (e.g. livestock, seed etc.) (A)	59.71 (35.07)	70 (14.14)	13.68 (15.26)	8.67 (10.07)
Proportion (%) quantity normally given out to relatives, friends etc. (as gifts) (B)	14.25 (8.09)	10 (0)	3.62 (3.58)	1.61 (2.09)
Proportion (%) normally sold (100- (A+B))	26.04	20.00	82.7	89.72

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources

Many individuals and households seeked additional sources of income beyond their primary occupations which are agriculture-related. These supplementary income sources can provide financial stability and opportunities for personal or economic growth for the individual or his household. The choice of additional income source can depend on an individual's skills, resources, interests, and goals. Diversifying income streams can enhance financial resilience and open up new opportunities for personal and financial growth. We are referring to those sources of income as non-farm income even though some of them such as sale of labour are farm related.

In the CWZ, quantitative information on non-farm income was obtained from only the WiHHs and only on salary and petty trading/food vending as given in Table 4.4. In the case of the NZ, remittances, petty trading/food vending, sale of firewood, and charcoal production, among others, were the important sources of non-farm income stated by HHHs. For WiHHs (women), remittances, transportation services, petty trading/food vending and food processing, among others, were the ones stated as the main non-farm sources of income (Table 4.4). The amounts indicated are the average amounts of income respondents said they obtained from these stated activities. It is clear from the table that non-farm sources of income are far more important in the NZ than in the CWZ despite the fact that NZ is more rural than the CWZ.

Table 4.4: Non-farm income sources for women in CWZ, and men and women in NZ (in CFA Franc)

Non-farm income source	Mean	Std. Deviation	Maximum	Maximum
CWZ – WiHH (women)				
Salary	200,000.00	-	200,000.00	200,000.00
Petty trading/food vending	27,500.00	31,819.805	50,000	5,000
NZ – HHH (men)				
Remittances	960,000.00	.	960,000	960,000
Petty trading/food vending	330,000.00	17,1755.64	500,000	50,000
Sale of firewood	250,000.00	.	250,000	250,000
Charcoal production	170,000.00	98,488.58	250,000	60,000
Food processing	162,500.00	101,036.30	250,000	75,000
Sale of Labour	150,000.00	.	150,000	150,000
Salary	60,000.00	.	60,000	60,000
NZ – WiHH (women)				
Remittances	630,000.00	466,690.48	960,000	300,000
Transportation services (carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)	250,000.00	-	250,000	250,000
Petty trading/food vending	185,000.00	116,726.18	300,000	25,000
Food processing	116,666.67	115,470.05	250,000	50,000
Salary	100,000.00	-	100,000	100,000
Sale of labour	50,000.00	-	50,000	50,000
Sale of firewood	45,000.00	-	45,000	45,000
Charcoal production	43,333.33	2,886.75	45,000	40,000

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

The quantitative information given in Tables 4.4, could not capture a lot of information especially as only a few respondents gave estimates of their non-farm incomes. It is difficult to income estimations by recall. Thus information in Table 4.4 can only be regarded as reasonable estimates. A qualitative method was therefore also used to obtain some information on the main sources of non-farm income. Respondents were asked to rank the sources of income from 1 to 5, 1 being the most important and 5 the least important. It was used to triangulate (cross check) and also obtain extra information. The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies⁴, was used. The weighted scores give farmers' relative perception of the importance of the non-farm income sources based on their experiences over time. It is worth noting that both the men and women in both zones responded very well to the qualitative questions. Figures 4.1 and 4.2 give the qualitative results depicting the relative importance of the different sources of non-farm income as perceived by HHHs and WiHHs respectively in the two zones. Petty trading/food

⁴ See Appendix 3 for results obtained and the computation of the weighted scores of ranked frequencies.

vending is a major source of income to both men and women in the two zones. Remittances are however limited to only men in both zones. All details are given in the two figures. They clearly show the zonal and gender differences. It is also worth comparing the qualitative and the quantitative information (i.e. Figures 4.1 and 4.2, and Table 4.4).

Figure 4.1: Non-farm sources of income in the past one year - HHs

Figure 4.2: Non-farm sources of income in the past one year - WiHHs

4.4 Expenditure by Households

Average expenditure per HHHs and WiHHs on various items are presented in Table 4.5. Households (HHHs and WiHHs) in CWZ spent an average of 1,384,573.50 CFA (about 13,568.93 Euros) in the past year (2022) on all items, while households in NZ spent about 1,510,442.10 CFA (about 14,802.45 Euros). Expenditures in CWZ were mainly on funerals and social activities, school expenses, food grains, livestock inputs and farm inputs. In the case NZ, the expenses were largely on traditional and orthodox health care, clothing, transportation, school expenses, farm inputs and food grains (Table 4.5). The figures are indicative since it is quite difficult to remember most of the expenditures. It is also obvious that some expenditures were not captured in both areas.

Table 4.5: Household expenditure on various items by men (HHH) and women (WiHH) in 12 months (2022/2023)

Central West Zone			NorthZone		
	HHH	WiHH		HHH	WiHH
	Amount per HH per annum (CFA Franc)			Amount per HH per annum (CFA Franc)	
Funerals and other social activities	94,400.00	155,187.50	Traditional health care for HH members	186,000.00	100,000.00
Schooling expenses	92,083.30	188,375.00	Clothing	104,428.60	71,536.40
Food (grain)	48,833.30	169,500.00	Transportation (general)	77,000.00	-
Livestock inputs	24,444.40		Schooling expenses	72,638.50	75,143.40
Farm inputs	0.00	246,250.00	Farm inputs	72,316.70	96,537.40
Orthodox health care for HH members	0.00	150,000.00	Orthodox health care for HH members	62,771.40	85,576.90
Soup ingredients		85,000.00	Food (grain)	62,365.50	86,764.90
Firewood/Charcoal		130,500.00	Transportation (for farm activities)	50,000.00	32,000.00
Total	259,761.00	1,124,812.50	Irrigation water charges	40,000.00	38,000.00
HH Total (CFA Franc)	1,384,573.50		Other (Specify)	40,000.00	0.0
HH Total (Euro equivalent)		13,568.93	Funerals and other social activities	31,160.00	0.0
			Livestock inputs	11,285.70	114,916.70
			Total	809,966.40	700,475.70
			HH Total	1,510,442.10	
			HH Total (Euro equivalent)	14,802.45	

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

As discussed with respect to non-farm income sources, qualitative information can complement the quantitative information to give greater insight into choices made by household members. The weighted scores of ranked frequencies method was again used to obtain information on HHHs' perceived relative expenditure patterns. The results are as given in Figure 4.3. See Appendix 4 for the data used for the diagram.

Figure 4.2: HHHs expenditure in 12 months (2022) – (weighted averages of main expenditure items)

The results confirm expenditures on the main items as indicated in Table 4.5 but the relativities are quite different in several cases. Food grains are, for example, the most important expenditure item indicated in Figure 4.2 but that is not the items with the highest expenditures. Also schooling expenditure are high as in Table 4.5 but Figure 4.2 does not indicate that they regard it as the most important. The results indicate the reality. High expenditures do not necessarily imply high relative importance. Some less unimportant items have high prices.

CHAPTER 5

HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY

5.1 Household Food Security

Even though farming is the main occupation of rural households in Senegal, many households run out of food in some years, making them food insecure. In the survey, respondents were asked to indicate which months in the past two years and past one year their households ran out of food. Table 5.1 shows that there have been food shortages in the two zones in almost all months except January and February in the 2021 farming season in the NZ . Table 5.1 further explains that food shortages are more pronounced in the months of July to November in the NZ but almost every month in the CWZ. The implication is that there is higher food insecurity in the CWZ than in NZ .

Table 5.1: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022

Month in which there was shortage of cultivated food	Central WestZone		NorthZone	
	HHHs		HHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
January	9 (7.7)	8 (7.7)	0	6 (8.2)
February	10 (8.5)	8 (7.7)	0	6 (8.2)
March	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	1(4.8)	6 (8.2)
April	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	1(4.8)	6 (8.2)
May	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	1(4.8)	5 (6.8)
June	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	1(4.8)	4 (5.5)
July	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	2 (9.5)	4 (5.5)
August	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	3 (14.3)	6 (8.2)
September	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	5 (23.8)	8 (11.0)
October	10 (8.5)	9 (8.7)	5 (23.8)	9 (12.3)
November	9 (7.7)	8 (8.7)	2 (9.5)	8 (11.0)
December	9 (7.7)	8 (8.7)	0	5 (6.8)

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

5.2 Household Dietary Diversity

5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day - HHH

All household heads (men) in the CWZ had consumed food made from grains or cereals (primarily maize and rice-based), oil/fats, butter, sugar, and/or honey the day before the interview. Nearly all household heads also consumed foods such as starchy staples, i.e., root and tuber-based diets, leafy vegetables, and fruits (Table 5.2). The vast majority of household heads in the CWZ had consumed foods such as condiments and fresh/dried or shellfish (seafood) the day before the interview. About half of the household heads in the CWZ consumed meat and other organs, while approximately 47% each consumed legume-based diets like beans and other dairy products. Eggs were the least consumed food group by household heads in the CWZ the day before the interview. A significant portion (73%) of household heads interviewed showed high dietary diversity, while 27% showed moderate dietary diversity.

In the NZ, all household heads (men) consumed food made from grains or cereals-based diets and other dietary condiments (Table 5.2). Nearly all household heads in the NZ also consumed foods made from sugar and/or honey and fresh/dried or shellfish (seafood) the day before the interview. The vast majority (73%) of household heads consumed oil/fats or butter. At least about two-thirds or fewer of the household heads in the NZ consumed vegetables and tuber-based diets. Nearly half (49%) consumed eggs, while 33% consumed meat and organs, 30% consumed fruits, 27% consumed dairy products, and 9% consumed legume-based diets like beans. Legume-based diets were the least consumed food group. In the Senegal River Valley, a relatively small proportion (24%) of the interviewed household heads showed high dietary diversity, with 73% showing moderate dietary diversity and 3% showing low dietary diversity.

Whereas both regions consume staple foods, there are differences in the variety of foods consumed. The CWZ also includes starchy staples, leafy vegetables, and fruits in their diet, whereas the NZ shows consumption of fewer vegetables and tuber-based diets. In the CWZ, about half of the household heads consumed meat and other organs, while in the NZ, only 33% consumed meat and organs. Similarly, the consumption of dairy products was higher in the CWZ (about 47%) compared to the NZ (27%). Eggs were the least consumed food group in the CWZ, whereas in the NZ, nearly half consumed eggs. Legume-based diets were consumed by approximately 47% of household heads in the CWZ but only by 9% in the NZ, indicating a significant difference in dietary preferences.

Understanding these differences can inform targeted nutritional interventions. For instance, in the NZ, where the consumption of vegetables and legumes is lower, interventions promoting the consumption of these foods may be beneficial for improving overall nutrition. Health policies should consider regional dietary patterns to address specific nutritional needs. For example, in regions with low consumption of certain food groups like vegetables or legumes, policies can focus on increasing the availability and affordability of these foods. Public health campaigns can raise awareness about the importance of dietary diversity and encourage the

consumption of a variety of nutrient-rich foods, especially in regions where dietary diversity is low or where certain food groups are consumed less frequently.

Table 5.2: Household head Dietary Diversity (HDDS)

	Central West Zone (n = 15)		NorthZone (n = 33)	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	15	100	33	100
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	14	93.3	21	63.6
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	13	86.7	22	66.7
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	13	86.7	10	30.3
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	8	53.3	11	33.3
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	5	33.3	16	48.5
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, catfish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	12	80.0	29	87.9
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	7	46.7	3	9.1
Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	7	46.7	9	27.3
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	15	100	24	72.7
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	15	100	31	93.9
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, boabab?	12	80.0	33	100
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	0	0	1	3
Moderate	4	26.7	24	72.7
High	11	73.3	8	24.2

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHH

Households in the CWZ, all the women had consumed food made from grains or cereal products, as well as oil/fat or butter, on the day before the interview. Additionally, nearly all women interviewed had consumed foods made from starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, sugar or honey, fruits, seafood (fresh/dried or shellfish), and other food condiments such as coffee and vegetables (Table 5.3). Sixty percent of the women in households in the CWZ had consumed dairy products. Approximately 27% of the women had consumed legume-based diets including beans, meat and organs the day before the interview, while about 20% had consumed eggs, the least consumed food group. Notably, in the CWZ, a significant proportion (60%) of the interviewed women showed moderate dietary diversity, while 40% showed high dietary diversity.

Table 5.3: Women in household dietary diversity (WiHDDS)

	Central West Zone		NorthZone	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	15	100	34	100
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	14	93.3	22	64.7
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	12	80	22	64.7
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	13	86.7	7	20.6
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	4	26.7	16	47.1
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	3	20	12	35.3
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, catfish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	13	86.7	31	91.2
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. "Red-red" etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	4	26.7	4	11.8
Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	9	60	20	58.8
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	15	100	25	73.5
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	14	93.3	34	100
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, baobab?	13	86.7	32	94.1
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	0	0	0	0
Moderate	9	60	26	76.5
High	6	40	8	23.5

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the NZ, all women in households consumed food made from grains or cereals-based diets as well as sugar or honey (Table 5.3). Nearly all of them had also consumed foods made from other food condiments and seafood (fresh/dried or shellfish). At least two-thirds or more of the women in households had consumed oils and fats, vegetables, and tuber-based diets. Additionally, half of the women in households had consumed dairy products the day before the interview. However, about 47% of women in the NZ had consumed meat and/or organs, while 35% had consumed eggs, and 21% had consumed fruits. Legume-based products were the least consumed food groups. Notably, in the NZ, a relatively high proportion (76.5%) of the interviewed women in households showed moderate dietary diversity, while 23.5% showed low dietary diversity.

While there are similarities in the consumption of staple foods and moderate dietary diversity between the two regions, differences exist in the variety of consumed foods in the CWZ and the NZ. Both regions include staple foods and diverse food consumption, but there are disparities in the variety of foods consumed by women. The CWZ also includes starchy staples, fruits, and a higher proportion of dairy product consumption, whereas the NZ shows consumption of vegetables and tuber-based diets. In the NZ, a higher percentage of women consumed meat and/or organs (47%) compared to the CWZ. However, fruit consumption was higher in the CWZ (20%) compared to the SRVZ (21%). Legume-based products were the least consumed food groups in the NZ, indicating a preference for other food types. However, in the CWZ, approximately 27% of women consumed legume-based diets, suggesting a relatively higher acceptance of legumes. Understanding these differences can inform targeted nutritional interventions. For example, in regions with lower consumption of certain food groups like vegetables or legumes, interventions promoting the consumption of these foods may be beneficial for improving overall nutrition. Additionally, in regions with higher meat consumption like the NZ, policies can focus on ensuring access to lean protein sources and promoting balanced diets. Raising awareness about the importance of dietary diversity and encouraging the consumption of a variety of nutrient-rich foods, especially in regions where dietary diversity is low or where certain food groups are consumed less frequently, can also contribute to improved health outcomes.

CHAPTER 6

HOUSEHOLD RESOURCES AND USE

6.1 General Changes in Land Use Over Time

6.1.1 Overall changes over 10 to 50 years

Over time, land use patterns have undergone significant transformations driven by various factors such as technological advancements, economic developments, population growth, and changing societal preferences. These changes over the past 10, 30, and 50 years have reshaped landscapes and ecosystems globally. From traditional agrarian societies to urbanized environments, the evolution of land use reflects human adaptation and exploitation of natural resources. In understanding these general changes in the CWZ and NZ, Tables 6.1 and 6.2 provide perceptions of the varied changes over time.

Over time, land use change in Senegal is evident. Generally, over the past 10 to 50 years, the change in indigenous crops is the most common measure of the change in land use for household heads. From the KIIs, it may be because climate change has given rise to the need to change cultivation practices. Therefore, farmers may cultivate other species instead of indigenous crops or change land use entirely. In the CWZ and the NZ, wildlife changes are important in the discussion on general land use change over the past 10 to 50 years for household heads (Table 6.1).

Table 6.1: HHHs' perceptions of general changes in land use overtime (past 10 to 50 years)

Item	Central West Zone		Senegal River Valley Zone	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Indigenous crops	9	42.9	18	28.1
Indigenous Trees	1	4.8	18	28.1
Indigenous livestock	1	4.8	0	0.0
Wildlife	5	23.8	2	3.1
Farming systems (production practices)	5	23.8	16	25.0
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0	6	9.4

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For the women in households, their main general changes in land use over the past 10 to 50 years are related to indigenous crops, indigenous livestock, indigenous trees, and farming system practices in CWZ, while for the women in households in NZ, main land use over time is related to indigenous crops, indigenous trees, and wildlife (Table 6.2). Curiously, there was little or no perceived change in waterbodies and wetlands by women in households.

Table 6.2: WiHHs’ perceptions of general changes in land use overtime (past 10 to 50 years)

Item	Central West Zone		NorthZone	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Indigenous crops	9	50.0	20	35.7
Indigenous Trees	2	11.1	20	35.7
Indigenous livestock	4	22.2	0	0.0
Wildlife	1	5.6	14	25.0
Farming systems (production practices)	2	11.1	1	1.8
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	1	1.8
Total	18	100.0	56	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Both household heads and women in the two zones of Senegal show awareness of land use changes over 10 to 50 years but with different focuses (Tables 6.1 and 6.2). Household heads primarily note a shift away from indigenous crops due to climate change, leading to altered crop production practices. They also emphasize wildlife changes. In contrast, women in households offer a broader perspective, including alterations in crops, livestock, trees, and farming practices, especially in the CWZ. In the NZ, women also consider changes in crops, trees, and wildlife. Interestingly, they perceive little to no change in waterbodies and wetlands.

These varied perspectives focus on the intricate nature of land use change and its diverse impacts. Household heads' emphasis on indigenous crops suggests vulnerability to climate change, necessitating adaptive agricultural strategies. Conversely, women's broader considerations indicate a general understanding of ecosystem dynamics. The difference in perceptions about waterbodies and wetlands suggests potential differences in environmental awareness or household roles.

6.1.2 Perceptions of land use changes by HHHs and WiHHs over the past 10 years

Over the past decade, significant shifts in land use patterns have occurred, particularly concerning households and women's roles. Tables 6.3, 6.4, and 6.5 explore the perspectives of both HHHs and WiHHs, shedding light on their respective roles and perceptions in shaping land use dynamics.

Table 6.3 indicates that HHHs in the CWZ perceive worsening trends in land use patterns for indigenous crops, indigenous trees, shrubs, indigenous livestock, and wildlife. Few household heads in this region observe improvements in indigenous crops and livestock. Conversely, household heads in the NZ perceive positive changes in indigenous crops, indigenous trees, irrigated agriculture, and farming systems (Table 6.4). While wildlife is perceived to be deteriorating by most households in the NZ, opinions are mixed regarding indigenous livestock and waterbodies/wetlands. Half of the respondents perceive improvements in indigenous livestock, while the other half see a worsening trend. Similarly, opinions are divided on waterbodies/wetlands, with half perceiving no change and the other half noting improvements in the situation concerning land use in the NZ (Table 6.3).

Table 6.3: General changes in land use according to HHHs in CWZ over the past 10 years

Item	Central West Zone					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Indigenous crops	2	22.2	0	0.0	7	77.8
Indigenous Trees	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Indigenous livestock	1	20.0	0	0.0	4	80.0
Wildlife	0	0.0	1	20.0	4	80.0
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irrigated agriculture	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farming systems (production practices)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 6.4: General changes in land use by HHHs in NZ over the past 10 years

Item	NorthZone					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Indigenous crops	12	66.7	3	16.7	3	16.7
Indigenous Trees	11	64.7	4	23.5	2	11.8
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Indigenous livestock	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Wildlife	5	31.3	1	6.3	10	62.5
Waterbodies/wetlands	3	50.0	3	50.0	0	0.0
Irrigated agriculture	2	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farming systems (production practices)	2	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 6.5 indicate that women in households (WiHHs) in the CWZ perceive worsening trends in land use patterns for indigenous crops and wildlife. While farming systems (production practices) are perceived to be improving by most women in households in this area, opinions are divided regarding indigenous livestock and indigenous trees. Half of the respondents perceive improvements in indigenous livestock and indigenous trees, while the other half see a worsening trend.

Conversely, households in the NZ perceive positive changes in indigenous crops and indigenous trees. While wildlife, waterbodies/wetlands, and farming systems (production

practices) are perceived to be deteriorating by most households in the NZ , few women in households believe that the situation for indigenous crops has remained the same (Table 6.6)

Table 6.5: Changes in land use as perceived by WiHHs in CWZ over the past 10 years

Item	Central West Zone					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Indigenous crops	4	44.4	0	0.0	5	55.6
Indigenous Trees	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Indigenous livestock	2	50.0	0	0.0	2	50.0
Wildlife	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irrigated agriculture	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farming systems (production practices)	2	100	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 6.6: Changes in land use as perceived by WiHHs in NZ over the past 10 years

Item	NorthZone					
	Getting better		Same		Getting worse	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Indigenous crops	16	80.0	3	15	1	5.0
Indigenous Trees	16	80.0	0	0.0	4	20.0
Shrubs	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Indigenous livestock	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Wildlife	6	42.9	0	0.0	8	57.1
Waterbodies/wetlands	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Irrigated agriculture	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farming systems (production practices)	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

6.1.3 Comparison of land use changes/transitions in the past 5, 10, 30 and 50 years in the zones as perceived by HHHs and WiHHs

This section provides an overview of land use changes and transitions over the past 5, 10, 30 and 50 in the CWZ and NZ . Tables 6.7 and 6.8 present descriptions of land use changes/transitions over time by HHHs and WiHHs respectively within the zones.

Table 6.7 gives the descriptions by HHHs of land use changes/transitions over the past years, especially concerning compound farmlands and bush farmlands, in relation to cultivated land, natural forests, and grazing lands, among others, in the CWZ and NZ . Fifty years ago, compound farmlands and bush farmlands were part of the natural forest/woodland. They have been characterized as irregular cultivated land and grazing land/grassland over the past 5 to 50 years, with compound farmlands primarily serving as grazing land/grassland. Household heads in the CWZ perceive that the phenomenon of bush farmlands becoming bare ground occurred a decade ago. In the case of the NZ, fifty years ago, most household heads perceived compound farmlands, bush farmlands, and other previously used lands as natural forest/woodland. This perception diminished slightly for bush farmlands 30 years ago. Compound farmlands and bush farmlands underwent irregular cultivation from 10 to 50 years ago, with a similar trend observed in other previously used lands 10 years ago in the NZ. While compound farmlands, bush farmlands, and other previously used lands were described as bare grounds 30 to 50 years ago in the NZ, open woodlands were primarily associated with compound farmlands and other previously used lands 30 years ago. Most household heads perceive compound farmlands, bush farmlands, and other previously used lands as cultivated from 5 to 50 years ago. Others note the use of other lands for grazing purposes 10 to 30 years ago in the NZ.

The descriptions provided by WiHHs for land use changes/transitions over the past 5, 10, 30 and 50 years, especially concerning compound farmlands and bush farmlands, are related to cultivated land, natural forests, irregular cultivated land, and bare ground in the CWZ and NZ are as presented in Table 6.8. In the recent past (5 to 30 years ago), most compound farmlands and bush farmlands are cultivated lands. Fifty years ago, this phenomenon was not observed for bush farmlands but was for compound farmlands. WiHHs in the CWZ describe natural forests used for compound farmlands and bush farmlands as a 50 years ago phenomenon. Irregular cultivation of compound farmlands and bush farmlands has been an occurrence for 30 years ago, albeit with few perceptions. From 5 to 10 years ago, irregular cultivation was perceived by women in households to occur on compound farmlands in the CWZ. Few women in households in the CWZ perceive that the phenomenon of compound farmlands becoming bare ground occurred 50 years ago. With regards to the NZ, most women perceived compound farmlands, bush farmlands, and other previously used lands to be natural forest/woodland 30 to 50 years ago. They however believed that bush farmlands underwent irregular cultivation from 10 to 30 years ago.

Table 6.7: Land use changes/transition over time in Central West Zone and NorthZone as perceived by HHHs

Land Description	5 years ago						10 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Central West Zone												
Cultivated land	7	50.0	2	66.7	0	0.0	6	42.9	2	66.7	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	6	42.9	1	33.3	0	0.0	7	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	1	7.1	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	7.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	33.3	0	0.0
NorthZone												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	20.0	2	22.2	2	14.3	3	30.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0			0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	9	100.0	14	100.0	8	80.0	6	66.7	12	85.7	0	0.0
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	11.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	7	70.0

Land Description	30 years ago						50 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Central West Zone												
Cultivated land	10	71.4	3	100.0	0	0.0	9	69.2	1	33.3	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	15.4	1	33.3	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	3	21.4	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	7.7	1	33.3	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	1	7.1	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	7.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
NorthZone												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	3	21.4	0	0.0	3	33.3	8	57.1	9	90.0
Irregular cultivated land	4	44.4	9	64.3	0	0.0	2	22.2	4	28.6	0	0.0
Bare ground	1	11.1	1	7.1	7	70.0	1	11.1	2	14.3	1	10.0
Cultivated land	3	33.3	1	7.1			2	22.2	0	0.0	0	0.0
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	10.0	1	11.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	1	11.1	0	0.0	1	10.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	10.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 6.7: Land use changes/transition over time in Central West Zone and NorthZone as perceived by HHHs

Land Description	5 years ago						10 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Central West Zone												
Cultivated land	8	66.7	4	100.0	0	0.0	8	66.7	4	100.0	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	4	33.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	33.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
North Zone												
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	12.5	5	100.0	4	20.0	2	25.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	5	100.0	20	100.0	7	87.5	0	0.0	16	80.0		
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	75.0

Land Description	30 years ago						50 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%	Freq	Freq%
Central West Zone												
Cultivated land	10	90.9	2	50.0	0	0.0	9	81.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Natural forest/woodland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	9.1	4	100.0	0	0.0
Irregular cultivated land	1	9.1	2	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	9.1	0	0.0	0	0.0
NorthZone												
Natural forest/woodland	2	40.0	9	45.0	0	0.0	4	80.0	19	95.0	8	100.0
Irregular cultivated land	0	0.0	10	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	5.0	0	0.0
Bare ground	3	60.0	1	5.0	6	75.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cultivated land	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Dams/dugouts	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Grazing land/grassland	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	25.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

6.2 Yields Change Over Time

Yields change over time acknowledges the dynamic aspect of agricultural productivity, involving fluctuations in both quantity and quality of crops or livestock over various periods. This variability is influenced by factors such as environmental conditions, technological improvements, management practices, and socio-economic factors. Yields, whether in terms of crop output per acre or livestock productivity, seldom stay consistent. The following findings (Figures 6.1 to 6.4) on reasons of increase or decrease in yields over time are the perceptions of HHHs and WiHHs in the CWZ and NZ.

No information was obtained from HHHs in CWZ with respect to reasons for increase in the yields of some crops. In the NZ, increase in yields of some crops over time was attributed to fertile soils, good land management, effective crop management, sufficient use of fertilizer or manure, absence of labour constraints, available financial support, the use of improved planting materials, and to a much lesser extent reliable rainfall (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: Reasons for increase in yields over time by in NZ zone by HHHs (No information was obtained from CWZ)

Women in the CWZ, gave reasons for increase in yields over the past 5 years, but the women in NZ did not provide any information (Figure 6.2). In CWZ, women attributed the increase to fertile soils, effective crop management, good land management, sufficient use of fertilizer or manure, available financial support, and the use of improved planting materials.

Figure 6.2: Reasons given by WiHHS for increase in yields over time in CWZ

Questions were also asked on the reasons for decrease in yields of some crops over time. As given in Figure 6.3, HHHs in the CWZ identified unreliable rainfall, poor soil fertility, labour constraints, financial constraints, the presence of pests and diseases, and the use of local planting materials as reasons for the decrease in yields. HHHs in the NZ did not provide any information on reasons for decrease in yields. During focus group discussions, however, they gave reasons for the decline in yield. They emphasized that in the area, the soils are degraded, particularly due to continuous land cultivation, the advancement of salt, and the use of chemical fertilizers.

Figure 6.3 Reasons given by HHHs for decrease in yields over time in CWZ

According to the women in CWZ, unreliable rainfall, pests and diseases, poor soil fertility, financial constraints, labour constraints, low use of inputs, and weed management are the paramount reasons for the decrease in yields over time. In the NZ, the women identified pests and diseases, poor soil fertility, weed management, low use of inputs, and financial constraints as the reasons for the decline in yield (Figure 6.4).

Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields in CWZ and NZ

CHAPTER 7

AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES

7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices

Adopting ecologically sound farming practices is paramount for the sustainability of agriculture. This section delves into the multifaceted sphere of sustainable agriculture, focusing on crucial elements such as the knowledge and use of agroecological practices. It discusses the influencing factors steering the use of these practices, emphasizing their seamless integration into farming systems. Furthermore, the section explores the types and uses of agro-wastes, as well as the quantities generated by households, as integral components in nurturing a holistic and environmentally conscious approach to agriculture.

Agroecological practices play a pivotal role in fostering sustainable agriculture, and promoting environmentally friendly and resilient farming systems. Assessing the awareness and usage of these practices at both the CWZ and NZ and discerning nuanced differences between men and women – at the gender level, is crucial for understanding the effectiveness of sustainable farming initiatives as shown in Tables 7.1, 7.2, 7.3 and 7.4

Central West Zone

In the CWZ, men (HHHs) are aware of agroecological technologies such as farmyard manure, crop rotation, fallow, cover cropping, compost, and lime (Ash). Specifically, about 87% of men mentioned that they were aware of farmyard manure, 80% crop rotation, 33% fallow, 20% cover cropping and 13% compost (Table 7.1). About the same percentages used farmyard manure and crop rotation in 2022 and 5 years in the past. That means those practices had been part of their local knowledge over time. Use of the other practices in past years was by small proportions of farmers as shown in Table 7.1

Table 7.1: HHHs awareness and use agroecological technologies in Central West Zone

Agroecological technologies	Men (HHHs) n=15					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Farmyard manure	13	86.7	13	86.7	13	86.7
Crop rotation	12	80.0	12	80.0	12	80.0
Fallow	5	33.3	4	26.7	3	20.0
Cover cropping	3	20.0	3	20.0	2	13.3
Compost	2	13.3	1	6.7	0	0.0
Lime (Ash)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For women in the CWZ, the known agroecological technologies included farmyard manure, compost, crop rotation, fallow, cover cropping, and lime (Ash) (Table 7.2). Among these practices, farmyard manure is the most recognized, with 80% of women being aware of it. Also about 67% of the women mentioned that they are aware of compost as an agroecological practice. Sixty percent and 53% indicated awareness of crop rotation and fallow, respectively. For cover cropping and lime (using ash), 27% and 13%, respectively, mentioned them as agroecological practices they are aware of (Table 7.2).

With respect to usage of the agroecological practices by women in CWZ, it was minimal. Only about 7% and 27% used compost in 2022 and 5 years ago respectively and about 13% practiced cover cropping 5 years ago. It will be interesting to know why there has been decline in the use of compost and cover cropping by the women of CWZ. It was, however, stated during focus group discussions that organic manure is increasingly being used, mainly due to the high cost of fertilizer. This practice is predominantly adopted by producers affiliated with the cooperative and those who have received training. Arboriculture is also practiced for land protection.

Table 7.2: WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central West Zone

Agroecological technologies	Women (WiHHs) n=15					
	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Farmyard manure	12	80.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop rotation	9	60.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Fallow	8	53.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Cover cropping	4	26.7	0	0.0	2	13.3
Compost	10	66.7	1	6.7	4	26.7
Lime (Ash)	2	13.3	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

North Zone

In the NZ, men (household heads) mentioned over 10 agroecological practices that they are aware of. Key among them were crop rotation, farmyard manure, crop residue management, improved water management, groundwater use (with pumps) for dry season farming, fallow, and agroforestry (trees in farm). Specifically, about 43%, 37% and 31% of men are aware of crop rotation, farmyard manure, and crop residues management respectively. Also about 26% are aware of improved water management, 14% are aware of ground water use for dry season farming, and 11% each are aware of fallow and agroforestry (trees in farm). The other percentages are as given in Table 7.3. The men (HHHs) also indicated considerable high use of almost all the mentioned technologies in 2022 and 5 years ago (Table 7.3). That is very encouraging for the CIRAWA project. The farmers have considerable knowledge of the agroecological practices and all CIRAWA should do is how to improve upon the practices.

Table 7.3: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in NorthZone (n = 35)

Agroecological technologies	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Crop rotation	15	42.9	13	37.1	14	40.0
Farmyard manure	13	37.1	11	31.4	10	28.6
Crop residues management	11	31.4	10	28.6	10	28.6
Improved water management	9	25.7	9	25.7	3	8.6
Ground water use (with pumps) for dry season farming	5	14.3	5	14.3	5	14.3
Fallow	4	11.4	3	8.6	3	8.6
Agroforestry (trees in farm)	4	11.4	4	11.4	3	8.6
Mulching	3	8.6	3	8.6	3	8.6
Burying of weeds	3	8.6	2	5.7	3	8.6
Minimum/No tillage	2	5.7	2	5.7	2	5.7
Drip Irrigation	2	5.7	2	5.7	0	0.0
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	1	2.9	1	2.9	1	2.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

For women in the NZ, agroecological practices they had been aware of included improved water management, farmyard manure, crop residue management, fallow, crop rotation, and burying of weeds (Table 7.4). Among these practices, improved water management and farmyard manure are the most recognized, with about 37% and 9% of women, respectively, being aware of them. Only about 6% of the women mentioned that they were aware of crop residue management and fallow as agroecological practices and about 3% indicated awareness of crop rotation and burying of weeds.

In terms of the usage of these agroecological practices in the NZ, almost all the women who were aware of improved water management used it in the 2022 season or have ever used it 5 years ago. That is, however, the only practice they have used. None of the women practiced any of the other agroecological technologies in 2022 or in the past (Table 7.4)

While there are similarities in agroecological practices awareness between the CWZ and the NZ, differences in usage rates and other factors contribute to distinct gender dynamics and usage patterns in each zone (Tables 7.1 to 7.4). In the CWZ, both men and women are aware of similar agroecological practices, but men generally exhibit higher awareness and utilization rates. Conversely, in the NZ, while both men and women possess knowledge of agroecological practices, men demonstrate varying levels of awareness, particularly in practices such as crop rotation, farmyard manure, and crop residue management. Women in the NZ acknowledge these practices, but their utilization remains limited, primarily confined to improved water management.

Table 7.4 WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in NorthZone (n = 35)

Agroecological technologies	Awareness		Use in 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	3	8.6	0	0.0	0	0.0
Crop residues management	2	5.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
Improved water management	13	37.1	1	2.9	6	17.1
Ground water use (with pumps) for dry season farming	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Fallow	2	5.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
Agroforestry (trees in farm)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Mulching	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Burying of weeds	1	2.9	0	0.0	0	0.0
Minimum/No tillage	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Drip Irrigation	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

7.2 Factors Influencing Use of Agroecological Practices

The use of agroecological practices is influenced by various factors, and understanding these elements is crucial for promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural approaches. Tables 7.5, and 7.6, showcase the most widely used agroecological practices, highlighting key factors that determine their use and implementation across zones and genders. In the CWZ, the factors influencing men's and women's use of farmyard manure, crop rotation, fallow, cover cropping, and compost are mostly related (Table 7.5). For men, the determinants for the use of farmyard manure and crop rotation are associated with soil improvement (41% and 44%), high expected benefits (52% and 30%), low cost of technology (47% each), availability of inputs necessary for carrying out these practices (82% and 18%), soil quality improvement (44% and 56%) due to the prevalence of infertile land, low labour requirements for household heads to implement these practices (13% and 25%), and low risk (17% and 83%), respectively.

For WiHH in the CWZ, the determinants for compost use include availability of inputs (38%), low risks (31%), low cost of technology (29%), soil improvement (25%), and high expected benefits (23%). Regarding crop rotation, fallow, and farmyard manure, the determinants are low labour requirement (50%, 25%, and 0%, respectively), low risk (27%, 19%, and 19%, respectively), low cost of technology (21% each), soil improvement (19%, 22%, and 31%, respectively), and high expected benefits (20%, 20%, and 29%, respectively) (Table 7.5).

In summary, in the CWZ (Table 7.5), both men and women prioritize soil improvement, high expected benefits, and low-cost technology in their agricultural practices. However, notable

differences exist in their priorities and emphasis on certain determinants. Men generally have higher percentages associated with determinants such as farmyard manure and crop rotation, while women show higher percentages for factors like low labour requirement and low risk in crop rotation, fallow, and farmyard manure. Men place more significance on the availability of inputs for farmyard manure, whereas women focus more on input availability for composting.

Tables 7.5: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men and women in Central West Zone

Agroecological practices	Improves the soil		High expected benefits		Low cost of technology	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads (men)						
Farmyard manure	11	40.70	12	52.20	7	46.70
Crop rotation	12	44.40	7	30.40	7	46.70
Fallow	1	3.70	1	4.30	1	6.70
Cover cropping	2	7.40	2	8.70	0	0.00
Compost	1	3.70	1	4.30	0	0.00
Women in household						
Compost	8	25.00	8	22.90	8	28.60
Crop rotation	6	18.80	7	20.00	6	21.40
Fallow	7	21.90	7	20.00	6	21.40
Farmyard manure	10	31.30	10	28.60	6	21.40

Agroecological practices	Availability of inputs		Land is infertile		Low labour		Low risk	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Household heads (men)								
Farmyard manure	9	81.80	4	44.40	1	12.50	1	16.70
Crop rotation	2	18.20	5	55.60	2	25.00	5	83.30
Fallow	0	0.00	0	0.00	4	50.00	0	0.00
Cover cropping	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	12.50	0	0.00
Compost	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Women in household								
Compost	8	38.10	3	17.60	0	0.00	8	30.80
Crop rotation	1	4.80	3	17.60	2	50.00	7	26.90
Fallow	0	0.00	3	17.60	1	25.00	5	19.20
Farmyard manure	11	52.40	8	47.10	0	0.00	5	19.20

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the NZ, the factors influencing men's and women's use of farmyard manure, crop rotation, fallow, cover cropping, and compost are mostly related (Table 7.6). For men, the determinants for the use of crop rotation and farmyard manure are associated with soil improvement (22% and 24%), high expected benefits (24% and 21%), low cost of technology (27% each), availability of inputs necessary for carrying out these practices (0% and 71%), soil quality

improvement (28% and 24%) due to the prevalence of infertile land, low labour requirements for household heads to implement these practices (18% and 6%), and low risk (30% and 25%), respectively. Additionally, most men (43%) use crop rotation because they have the technical capability.

For women in households in the NZ (Table 7.6), the determinants for crop residues management use include low labour requirement (33%), low cost of technology (17%), soil quality improvement due to the prevalence of infertile land (11%), and land soil improvement (8%). Regarding improved water management, crop rotation, and farmyard manure, the determinants are availability of inputs (71%, 0%, and 29%), low cost of technology (67%, 0%, and 17%), soil improvement (58%, 8%, and 25%, respectively), prevalence of infertile land (56%, 7%, and 17%, respectively), low labour requirement (33%, 0%, and 33%, respectively), low risk (0%, 50%, and 50%, respectively), and high expected benefits (0%, 33%, and 67%, respectively).

Tables 7.6: Factors influencing use of agroecological practices by men and women in North Zone

Agroecological practices	Improves the soil		Land is infertile		High expected benefits		Low cost of technology	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Household head (men)								
Crop rotation	11	22.0	14	28.0	8	24.2	6	27.3
Farmyard manure	12	24.0	12	24.0	7	21.2	6	27.3
Crop residues management	6	12.0	6	12.0	6	18.2	2	9.1
Women in household								
Crop residues management	1	8.3	2	11.1	0	0.0	1	16.7
Improved water management	7	58.3	10	55.6	0	0.0	4	66.7
Crop rotation	1	8.3	1	5.6	1	33.3	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	3	25.0	3	16.7	2	66.7	1	16.7

Agroecological practices	Low risk		Low labour		Technically capable		Availability of inputs	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Household head (men)								
Crop rotation	6	30.0	3	17.6	3	42.9	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	5	25.0	1	5.9	0	0.0	5	71.4
Crop residues management	1	5.0	4	23.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
Women in household								
Crop residues management	0	0.0	1	33.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Improved water management	0	0.0	1	33.3	0	0.0	5	71.4
Crop rotation	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Farmyard manure	1	50.0	1	33.3	0	0.0	2	28.6

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

A summary for the NZ (Table 7.6) is that both men and women exhibit similarities and differences in the factors influencing their agricultural practices, reflecting their varying priorities and circumstances. Both genders prioritize soil improvement, high expected benefits, and low-cost technology. However, men tend to have higher percentages associated with determinants such as crop rotation and farmyard manure, while women show higher percentages for factors like low labour requirement, low risk, and high expected benefits in improved water management, crop rotation, and farmyard manure. Availability of inputs holds greater significance for women's use of improved water management and farmyard manure, while men prioritize technical capability for using crop rotation.

Zonal comparison

In both zones, agricultural priorities such as soil improvement and cost-effectiveness are shared among men and women. However, differences in emphasis on specific determinants exist between genders within each zone. In the NZ, both men and women prioritize soil improvement, high expected benefits, and low-cost technology. Men tend to focus more on factors like crop rotation and farmyard manure, emphasizing technical capability, while women prioritize factors such as low labour requirement, low risk, and high expected benefits, with a greater emphasis on input availability for practices like improved water management and farmyard manure. In the CWZ, however, both men and women prioritize soil improvement, high expected benefits, and low-cost technology, but notable differences exist. Men show higher percentages associated with determinants like farmyard manure and crop rotation, while women exhibit higher percentages for factors such as low labour requirement and low risk, placing more emphasis on input availability for composting.

7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes

7.3.1 Types of agro-wastes and their uses

Agro waste, which includes leftover plant materials, crop residues, and by-products, is generated as a by-product of farming and food processing. Tables 7.7, 7.8, 7.9 and 7.10 present the various types of agro waste and their applications in the CWZ and NZ, categorized by gender. Table 7.7 shows the various types of agro waste and their uses in the CWZ by men (household heads). The types of agro waste used by men include stovers from cereals, legumes, animal manure, waste from abattoirs and kitchen waste. Cereal stovers have diverse uses; they are either used as soil amendments (raw material for composting or mulching), serve as bedding or feed for livestock, a source of fuel for cooking, a source of income, and as raw material for local construction by men. Almost, a quarter (20%) of it is incorporated into the soil or used as mulch. More than half of the household heads use it as bedding or feed for livestock. A relatively small portion of men sells cereal stovers for income, uses it as a source of fuel for household cooking activities, and as a base material for composting. A little over a quarter (32%) men use cereal stovers as raw material for building.

For legume waste, the uses are related to incorporation into the soil or used as mulch, livestock feed/bedding and for composting (Table 7.7).

Table 7.7: Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Central West Zone

Types of Agro-Wastes	Uses of Agro waste					
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	5	20	1	4	13	52
Legumes	1	4	0	0	3	12
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	13	52	0	0	2	8
Waste from abattoirs	1	4	0	0	0	0
Kitchen wastes	3	12	0	0	3	12

Types of Agro-Wastes	Uses of Agro waste					
	Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	4	13	4	13	8	32
Legumes	0	0	1	4	0	0
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	4	13	8	32	1	4
Waste from abattoirs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kitchen wastes	0	0	1	4	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.8 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Central West Zone

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste					
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	4	16	1	4	13	52
Legumes	1	4	0	0	6	24
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	16	64	1	4	0	0
Kitchen wastes	8	32	0	0	8	32

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste					
	Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	3	12	6	24	8	32
Legumes	0	0	2	8	0	0
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	3	12	11	44	1	4
Kitchen wastes	1	4	5	20	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Like legumes, kitchen waste has similar uses, albeit substantial portions of kitchen waste are used to incorporate into soil/mulch. More than half (52%) of the men incorporate animal manure into the soil. Others (8%) use it to formulate feed for livestock, especially poultry, and as a source of fuel (13%). Aside from incorporating animal manure into the soil, composting is the next highest, with 32% using animal manure (Table 7.6).

Table 7.8 shows that women in the CWZ use agro waste to meet diverse needs. Cereal stovers, in particular, have various uses such as soil amendments (raw material for composting or mulching), serving as bedding or feed for livestock, a source of fuel for cooking, and an income source. The majority (52%) of it serves as bedding or feed for livestock. A significant proportion of women indicated it is used as building material, for composting, soil mulch and as a source of fuel energy for cooking. A relatively small portion of women indicated it is sold for income.

For legume waste, most women indicated (24%) that they use it as feed for livestock. A significant portion (8%) of women use it as composting material, or it is incorporated into the soil (4%) (Table 7.6). Substantial portions of animal manure are incorporated into the soil as mulch (64%), used for composting (44%), and serve as a source of fuel (12%) for women in the CWZ. A relatively small portion (4%) of women indicated that they sell animal manure for income. More than a quarter (32% each) of women indicated that kitchen waste is incorporated into the soil as mulch and/or used as livestock feed (Table 7.6). About 20% of the women indicated that kitchen waste is used for composting.

In the CWZ, both men and women actively utilize agro waste for various purposes, with some minor differences in specific applications. Men primarily use cereal stovers and legume waste for livestock bedding or feed, fuel, income generation, and construction material. They also utilize kitchen waste for soil incorporation or mulch, livestock feed, and fuel. Animal manure is mainly incorporated into the soil, used for livestock feed, and composting among men. Women in the CWZ employ agro waste for diverse needs, particularly cereal stovers for livestock, cooking fuel, and construction material. They also utilize legume waste for livestock feed, composting, and soil incorporation or mulch. Similarly, kitchen waste serves for soil mulching and livestock feed, while animal manure is heavily used for soil mulching, composting, and fuel.

Tables 7.9 and 7.10 illustrate the diverse uses of agro waste in the NZ for men (household heads) and women, respectively. In Table 7.9, men primarily use cereal stovers for livestock feed/bedding (56%), mulching (52%), sales (16%), or composting (12%). A small percentage (4%) uses stovers as fuel or building material. For legume waste, 12% is mulched, 8% used for livestock, and 4% for composting, with 4% sold. All men incorporate animal manure into the soil (100%), 72% use it for livestock, 68% for composting, 16% as energy, 8% for construction, and 4% for income. Traditionally, animal manure serves as a binding material in construction.

Table 7.9 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in NorthZone

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	13	52	4	16	14	56	1	4	3	12	1	4
Legumes	3	12	1	4	2	8	0	0	1	4	0	0
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	25	100	1	4	18	72	4	16	17	68	2	8
Wastes from abattoirs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kitchen wastes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.10 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Senegal River Valley Zone

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	1	4	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Legumes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	15	60	0	0	13	52	2	8	3	12	1	4
Wastes from abattoirs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kitchen wastes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Table 7.10 highlights women's use of agro waste like cereal stovers and animal manure. Cereal stovers are used for soil amendments or as livestock bedding/feed. Animal manure is primarily used for soil mulching (60%) and livestock feed (52%), with some for composting (12%), fuel (8%), and construction binding (4%). According to the survey, women don't sell agro waste.

Tables 7.9 and 7.10 provide insights into the utilization of different types of agricultural waste among household heads (men) and women in the NZ. Both men and women utilize cereal stovers primarily for livestock-related purposes like feeding and bedding. However, men also involve themselves in the sales of cereal stovers, a practice not observed among women. Similarly, both genders utilize animal manure for enriching soil and feeding livestock. Men,

however, exhibit a broader range of applications for animal manure, including energy production and construction, whereas women's usage tends to concentrate more on mulching and livestock feed. Notably, women do not participate in the sale of animal manure based on the survey. The focus group discussions confirmed that household waste, animal manure, fodder waste, kitchen waste, and all other waste are mainly used as soil conditioners. However, it has been noted that this waste is insufficient to amend all the land. Therefore, there is need for strategies to effectively utilize household waste so that it can improve all the soil.

7.3.2 Quantities of agro waste generated by households

The quantities of agro waste generated by households play a significant role in understanding the environmental impact of agricultural activities and the potential for recycling or reuse. Table 7.11 provides the average quantities of agro waste generated by household heads and women in the CWZ and the NZ in kilograms per acre in the 2022 season.

In the CWZ, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated (gathered) by men per acre in a season is 76.67 kg, with a standard deviation (SD) of 40.4. For women in the same zone, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated (gathered) is 100 kg. Men and women, on average, produce a comparable quantity of cereal stovers; however, women may be more involved in agricultural activities that produce cereal stovers, potentially reflecting differences in agricultural roles between genders within the CWZ. In the CWZ, women generate (gather) more waste from abattoirs than men, whereas in the NZ, men generate more waste from abattoirs than women (see Table 7.11).

Table 7.11 Quantities of agro waste generated per acre per season

Types of Agro wastes	Central West Zone				NorthZone			
	Men quantity generated		Women quantity generated		Men quantity generated		Women quantity generated	
	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev
Cereals (stovers)	76.67	40.415	100	-	40.77	16.053	36.67	20.817
Legumes	0	0	0	0	55	49.497	0	0
Grasses	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Animal manure	0	0	0	0	19.17	4.916	15.00	.000
Wastes from abattoirs	60	0	100	-	35	27.386	22.50	12.154

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

In the NZ, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated by men per acre per season is 40.77 kg, with a standard deviation (SD) of 16.05. The average quantity of legume waste generated is 55 kg, with an SD of 49.5. The average quantities of animal manure and waste generated (gathered) from abattoirs are 19.2 kg and 35 kg, respectively, with standard deviations of 4.9 and 27.4. For women in the same zone, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated is 36.7 kg, with an SD of 20.8, and the average quantity of animal manure is 15 kg. The average quantity of waste from abattoirs is 22.5 kg, with an SD of 12.1.

CHAPTER 8

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES

8.1 Evidence of Climate Change

According to the household heads in CWZ, the perceived evidence of climate change includes temperature increases, decreases in rainfall, and the emergence of new insects (Figure 8.1). For household heads in NZ, the perceived evidence of climate change is similar to that of CWZ, with the addition that men in NZ also perceive an increase in new crop species. These observations imply that climate change is impacting both zones in comparable ways, though with some variations, potentially affecting local agriculture and ecosystem dynamics.

Figure 8.1: Household heads perceived evidence of climate change

For the WiHH, climate change is perceived as an increase or decrease in temperature, changing rainfall patterns, prolonged droughts, and the emergence of new insects in both CWZ and NZ. Increases in floods and the appearance of new crop species are peculiar to women in NZ (Figure 8.2). These perceptions suggest that climate change is affecting both zones in similar ways, but with unique impacts in NZ that could influence local agricultural practices and the availability of resources for women.

Figure 8.2: Women in household perceived evidence of climate change

From the key informant interviews conducted, Climate change is evidenced by very high temperatures, irregular appearance of winds and a changing rainy season in recent years. These changes were attributed to pollution, deforestation, the intensification of agriculture, urbanization, and the exploitation of wood for heating.

Also, it was reported that certain species such as sorghum, millet, camels, and monkeys were present in the area but are currently almost non-existent. The disappearance of the species for crops was attributed to the long cycle (for millet) and the advancement of salt which made some of the soils unusable to farm crops. For the loss of animal species, deforestation and rapid urbanization are the main factors noted for their disappearance.

8.2 Climate Change Adaptation Measures

The climate change adaptation measures reported by the household heads in both CWZ and NZ are similar. They include the use of agroforestry, irrigated agriculture, drought-resistant crop varieties, crop-livestock integration, crop diversification, planting of trees in the form of woodlots, and early warning systems (Figure 8.3). The use of climate risk insurance was only reported by the men in NZ as a climate adaptation strategy. These adaptation measures suggest a comprehensive approach to mitigating the impacts of climate change, although the unique reliance on climate risk insurance by men in NZ indicates zonal and gender-specific strategies that might require targeted support and resources.

Figure 8.3: Household heads climate change adaptation measures

While women in both CWZ and NZ also practice similar adaptation strategies as the men, the use of climate risk insurance was reported as an additional strategy by the women in NZ (Figure 8.4). This indicates that women in NZ might have a greater need for financial protection against climate-related risks, suggesting that tailored financial products and support systems could be beneficial in enhancing their resilience to climate change.

From the Key Informant Interviews, solutions proffered by the interviewees to improve adaptation to climate change consists of improving the practice of agroforestry, setting up artificial forests and strengthening water and forestry agencies and officials as important stakeholders in the fight against the effects of climate change.

Figure 8.4: Women in household climate change adaptation measures

8.3 Anti-environmental practices

Many community activities may harm the environment or undermine efforts to protect it. These practices can have a range of negative impacts on ecosystems, biodiversity, and human health. In Senegal, three main activities were reported as anti-environmental. These were deforestation, bushfires, and plastic waste.

Deforestation was reported to be the effect of mainly illegal logging for charcoal production and firewood cutting which was attributed to women in their search for fuelwood for cooking and also for sale for additional income. It was further noted that the practice was also common among breeders for fodder, and by farmers as they ploughed their fields. Fires were also considered anti-environmental with the main perpetrators being smokers and also by farmers in the event of burning of agricultural residues. Further, exposure to plastic waste was noted. This was aggravated mainly by women disposing of waste like baby diapers and packaging.

To improve the situation, the FGD mentioned the importance of planting trees for livestock (fodder species), secondly putting in place support measures for the management of plastic waste and finally planting species against salinization.

CHAPTER 9

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

9.1 Summary

This report sought to define the baseline characteristics in Senegal with the aim of providing information on farmers' and communities' needs and requirements, their resource availability and use as well as identification of the available agro-ecological practices in the CWZ and the NZ. The report also provides baseline information on the socio-economic and environmental factors on which important decisions can be made in the project and serve as a basis for monitoring and evaluating project progress and effectiveness during implementation.

The socio-demographic characteristics of the household in Senegal are typical of most African households. In the two zones sampled, the households were generally male headed households with a majority of the population being indigenes except for the women in the CWZ where about 40% were non indigenes. Generally, the respondents had spent over 20 years in the area and therefore conversant with the practices and challenges of the area. Their household sizes were generally high in the two areas averaging about 19 people in the CWZ and 13 people per household in the NZ .

Arable farming is an important occupation in the area with about 97% of the respondents in the NZ and 17.6% in the CWZ engaged in it. The average landholding for farming in the CWZ is 15.5 acres and that of the NZ is 5.5 acres while the land is mainly acquired by inheritance. The main soil amendment practices in the NZ and CWZ are crop rotation, use of manure (organic materials) and the use of fertilizer amongst others. Similarly in the CWZ, the use of manure (organic materials) is the main practice (40%), followed by crop rotation (33%) and fertilizer (13%). The responses from WiHH are similar to the responses of HHH in both zones, confirming the use of crop rotation and organic materials as main soil amendment practices in the zones. This may be an indication of the possibility of success of agroecological practices in the area since most practices are indigenous and agro-based.

The primary crop production constraint in the CWZ is erratic rainfall, which is not listed among the top constraints in the NZ. In the NZ their main constraint is access to production inputs. Livestock rearing is also an important minor occupation. In the CWZ, men owned various types of livestock including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, non-ruminants such as donkeys, horses, and pigs, as well as poultry consisting of fowls (chickens), guinea fowls, and turkeys. There are distinct patterns in livestock ownership and management practices between men and women in the CWZ. Women tend to own fewer livestock than men, do, particularly in cattle, and non-ruminants. The women farms are mainly irrigated vegetable farms and that partly explains the small sizes. Both men and women in the NZ had a stable livestock ownership pattern with slight declines in sheep, goat, and fowl ownership.

Irrigation has the potential to improve crop yields. In Senegal, smallholder surface water and smallholder groundwater irrigation using diesel and petrol pumps, buckets jerry cans and solar pumps were the main irrigation types in the CWZ as well as the NZ. The major constraint mentioned was the high cost of production inputs (seeds, fertilizers etc.).

In many of the households sampled, the main source of income was from small-scale crop farming and livestock rearing. They however obtained other sources of income from other activities such as; illegal mining, artisanship, petty trading, food processing, remittances, gifts, salaries, and others.

Even though farming is the main occupation of rural households in Senegal, many households run out of food in some years, making them food insecure. In the previous farming season (2021) food shortages occurred in the two zones in almost all months except January and February. In the NZ, food shortages were more pronounced in the months of July to November but felt almost every month in the CWZ. Even though several factors contribute to higher yields, from the survey, the household heads in both the CWZ and NZ note fertile soils to be the major factor responsible for good yields followed by good crop and land management practices.

Agroecological practices play a pivotal role in fostering sustainable agriculture and promoting environmentally friendly and resilient farming systems. It was found that in both zones, men are primarily aware of and mention various agroecological practices, including farmyard manure, crop rotation, fallow, cover cropping, compost, and lime (Ash). In both zones, the topmost agricultural priority of soil improvement is shared among men and women. However, differences in emphasis on specific determinants exist between genders within each zone. Men tend to focus more on factors like crop rotation and farmyard manure, emphasizing technical capability, while women prioritize factors such as low labour requirement, low risk, and high expected benefits, with a greater emphasis on input availability for practices like improved water management and farmyard manure.

Farm waste is utilised in many applications. The most available waste was the stovers from cereals which are used for soil amendments or as livestock bedding/feed. However, men also involve themselves in the sales of cereal stovers, a practice not observed among women. Similarly, both genders utilize animal manure for enriching soil and feeding livestock. Men, however, exhibit a broader range of applications for animal manure, including energy production and construction, whereas women's usage tends to concentrate more on mulching and livestock feed. Notably, women do not participate in the sale of animal manure based on the survey. The focus group discussions confirmed that household waste, animal manure, fodder waste, kitchen waste, and all other waste are mainly used as soil conditioners. However, it has been noted that this waste is insufficient to amend all the land.

On the topical issue of climate change, the two zones best indicator was increased temperature. Solutions proffered by the interviewees to improve adaptation to climate change consist of improving the practice of agroforestry, setting up artificial forests, strengthening water and forestry agencies, and officials as important stakeholders in the fight against the effects of

climate change. In addition, three main activities were reported as anti-environmental. These were deforestation, bushfires, and plastic waste.

9.2 Recommendations

To foster resilient farming practices in Senegal several recommendations are proposed based on the data collected and analysed :

1. Promote Agroecological Techniques: Many of the farmers are aware and use some agroecological practices. The MACCLI (Manure-Agroforestry-Compost-Crop/Livestock Integration) agroecological technique should be adopted for the zones. The practices in MACCLI are complementary and synergistic. The technique also covers almost all the areas CIRAWA proposes as agroecological solutions, namely compost/vermicompost, household energy production, soil rehabilitation and reclamation (phytoremediation) and others. Households should be empowered technically and otherwise to adopt the technique (preferably in whole but can be in parts. The technique, if applied adequately will enhance soil fertility, ensure sustainable and resilient agricultural systems, improve water management, and mitigate the impacts of climate change.
2. Building capacity and institutional support: Strengthen agricultural institutions to support the adoption and scaling up of resilient farming practices through policies, regulations, and incentives
3. Strengthen farmer capacity and extension services: Provide training and extension services to farmers to enhance their skills in using agroecological practices to boost their food and nutritional security.
4. Health policies and campaigns: Public health campaigns should raise awareness about the importance of dietary diversity and encourage the consumption of a variety of nutrient-rich foods, especially in zones where dietary diversity is low or where certain food groups are consumed less frequently.
5. Our engagements and dialogues with stakeholders at national, sub-national, local and community levels should lead to the production of a National Agroecological Strategy Plan to redirect national endeavours toward sustainable agricultural and food systems. Agroecology is clearly the path to a viable and sustainable agricultural strategy for smallholder farmers. An agroecological plan for the country is in line with the CIRAWA aim at effective dialogue with national, sub-national and local level stakeholders, visibility of EC funding in the countries and ensuring the project's legacy (WP6). This could be follow-ups after CIRAWA.

The recommendations when implemented in a coordinated and participatory manner can build more resilience in the agricultural sector and therefore help the farmers adapt to climate change, reduce their vulnerability to food insecurity and improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers, in Senegal.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1:

The Method of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies (WSRF)

Relative importance of crop production constraints – Central West Zone - HHHs

Crop production constraints	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	Total Weighted score	% Weighted score
	Frequencies						
Erratic rainfall	9	2	2	0	0	59	30.4
Finance	2	4	1	3	1	36	18.6
Soil fertility	0	5	2	0	1	27	13.9
Pests and diseases	2	1	2	2	1	25	12.9
Access to prodn inputs	0	0	4	2	0	16	8.2
Access to extn services	0	0	2	0	0	6	3.1
Access to farming land	1	0	0	0	0	5	2.6
Small farm size	1	0	0	0	0	5	2.6
Land ownership	0	0	0	1	2	4	2.1
Access to farm land	0	0	1	0	0	3	1.5
Access to weather information	0	0	0	1	0	2	1.0
Weeds	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.5

Relative importance of crop production constraints – Senegal River Valley Zone - HHHs

Crop production constraints	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	Total Weighted Score	% Weighted score
	Frequencies						
Access to prodn inputs	1	11	8	2	2	79	15.8
Soil fertility	14	2	0	0	0	78	15.6
Pests and diseases	2	2	8	9	6	66	13.2
Finance	2	2	2	11	10	56	11.2
Weeds	0	10	0	2	8	52	10.4
Access to farming land	6	3	0	1	0	44	8.8
Erosion	0	0	11	1	1	36	7.2
Erratic rainfall	1	4	0	0	1	22	4.4
Labour	2	1	2	0	2	22	4.4
Access to extn services	1	1	0	4	3	20	4.0
Small farm size	0	4	0	0	0	16	3.2
Land ownership	0	1	0	0	0	4	0.8
Small farm size	0	0	0	1	0	2	0.4
Access to weather information	0	0	0	1	0	2	0.4

Appendix 2: Estimation of household income of harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		Total quantity harvested (in local units)		Price per unit (local currency)		Value of output (local currency)
1	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	(Q _{A1} x P _{A1}) + (Q _{B1} x P _{B1})
2.	A2	B2	Q _{A2}	Q _{B2}	P _{A2}	P _{B2}	(Q _{A2} x P _{A2}) + (Q _{B2} x P _{B2})
etc	A _i	B _i	Q _{A_i}	Q _{B_i}	P _{A_i}	P _{B_i}	(Q _{A_i} x P _{A_i}) + (Q _{B_i} x P _{B_i})
Equation for computation of the estimated household income from harvested crops (where n = number of household plots)							$N \sum_{i=1} ((Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i}))$
<p>A1 = crop A from plot 1; Q_{A1} = A1 harvested quantity; P_{A1} = Price of A1 B1 = crop B from plot 1; Q_{B1} = B1 harvested quantity; P_{B1} = Price of B1 Thus: A_i = Crop A from plot i; Q_{A_i} = A_i harvested quantity; P_{A_i} = Price of A_i etc.</p>							

Central West Zone – HHH

D1_1_Crop_1	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	D1_1_Crop_2	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Millet	9	224777.7778	181288.291	Groundnut	9	111277.78	123514.96
Maize	6	273333.3333	116390.1485	Beans (Cowpea)	5	130000	97467.943
Total	15	244200	155642.5392	Total	14	117964.29	111346.39

Millet/GN 336055.56

Maize/Beans 403333.33

739388.89

North Zone – HHH

D1_1_Crop_1	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	D1_1_Crop_2	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Rice	18	5649822.222	16193230.73	Rice	1	1024000	.
Groundnut	4	4044625	2858664.997	Groundnut	3	2133333.3	2444040.4
Beans (Cowpea)	1	0	.	Sweet potato	1	262500	.
Cassava	6	7433333.333	4695707.259	Pepper	2	6650000	5444722.2
Onions	6	1525583.333	1082536.116	Tomatoes	8	3841125	5489430.4
Mango	1	750000	.	Okro	4	1237875	1290776.8
Total	36	4788300	11660719.06	Onions	6	640458.33	696660.79
				Watermelon	1	0	.
				Aubergine	1	300000	.

				Total	27	2252213	3684308.1
Rice				5649822.22			
Groundnut/rice				5068625			
Cassava/Sweet potato				7695833.33			
Onions/Okro/Pepper				2763458.33			
				21177738.89			

Appendix 3:

The Method of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies (WSRF)

Relative importance of non-farm sources of income in the past one year - HHHs

Non-Agric source of income	Senegal River Valley Zone							Central West Zone						
	Weighted scores							Weighted scores						
	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score%	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score%
Sale of Labour	5	16	3	3	1	28	8	5	4	0	0	0	9	6.9
Remittances	20	24	9	6	1	60	17	5	28	3	0	0	36	27.7
Gifts	5	8	3	0	2	18	5	0	0	15	3	0	18	13.7
Sale of fruits	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	3.1
Petty trading/food vending	50	16	18	0	0	84	24	10	0	6	0	0	16	12.2
Salary	10	4	6	6	5	31	9	15	0	0	0	0	15	11.5
Transportation services	5	0	3	3	3	14	4	0	4	0	0	0	4	3.1
Artisanship	15	0	0	0	0	15	4	5	0	0	0	0	5	3.8
Sale of firewood	5	12	0	0	1	18	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Charcoal production	15	4	9	0	0	28	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Illegal/small scale mining	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Food processing	20	8	9	3	2	42	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Pension	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	15	0	0	0	0	9	11.5
Others	5	8	3	0	1	0	5	5	4	0	0	0	15	6.9

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023

Relative importance of non-farm sources of income in the past one year - WiHHs

Non-agric source of income	Senegal River Valley Zone							Central West Zone						
	Weighted scores							Weighted scores						
	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score %	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score%
Sale of Labour	10	4	0	3	0	17	5	5	0	0	0	0	5	3
Remittances	35	16	12	3	0	66	18	20	16	3	0	0	39	26
Gifts	5	32	3	6	1	47	13	0	8	6	3	1	18	12
Sale of fruits	10	0	0	0	0	10	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Petty trading/food vending	50	32	3	0	1	86	23	30	8	12	0	0	50	34
Salary	10	0	6	15	5	36	10	20	4	0	0	0	24	16
Transportation services	10	0	0	3	2	15	4	0	0	3	0	0	3	2
Artisanship	5	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sale of firewood	0	4	6	0	1	11	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Charcoal production	0	12	0	0	2	14	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Illegal/small scale mining	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Food processing	25	8	12	9	0	54	14	0	0	0	6	0	6	4
Pension	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	3
Others	10	4	0	0	1	15	4		0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Appendix 4:

Household expenditure in 12 months (at time of survey) – HHH (Weighted scores of ranked frequencies method)

Expenditure in the last year	Senegal River Valley Zone							Central West Zone						
	Weighted scores							Weighted scores						
	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score %	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score%
Food (grain)	140	4	0	0	0	144	30	60	8	3	0	0	71	34
Livestock inputs	0	8	12	2	0	22	5	5	8	18	0	0	31	15
Schooling expenses	0	0	0	20	0	20	4	5	0	0	0	0	5	2
Funerals and other social activities	0	0	0	4	8	12	3	5	8	3	2	0	18	9
Farm inputs	5	60	15	8	0	88	19	0	4	0	0	1	5	2
Orthodox health care for HH members	5	16	39	10	5	75	16	0	12	6	8	0	26	13
Schooling expenses	0	24	21	0	3	48	10	0	16	3	0	0	19	9
Church & other religious contributions	0	0	0	2	2	4	1	0	4	0	0	2	6	3
Clothing	0	0	0	4	12	16	3	0	0	6	2	2	10	5
Transportation (for farm activities)	0	4	0	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
Transportation (general)	0	0	3	0	1	4	1	0	0	0	10	2	12	6
Remittances/ Gifts	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	1
Meat and Dairy	0	12	0	0	1	13	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	0	0	3	2	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Irrigation water charges	0	0	3	2	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Traditional health care for HH members	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amenities	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other	10	0	0	0	0	10	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, May/June 2023